

**Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability
of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through
Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge
Solutions' Gains**

**D5.1: Planning and setup handbook, and operational
management report (1st version)**

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**Funded by
the European Union**

Grant Agreement No.	101060294		
Project Acronym	XGain		
Project Title	Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains		
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions		
Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-03		
Project Start Date	September 1 st , 2022	Project End Date	August 31 st , 2025
Project URL	xgain-project.eu		
Work Package	WP5 Technology Validation and Impact Assessment		
WP Lead Beneficiary	eBOS		
Deliverable type¹ Dissemination level²	R PU		
Contractual due date	30 November 2023	Actual submission date	30 November 2023
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Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	01/09/2023	5	ToC	Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS)
V0.9	10/11/2023	90	All sections completed & contributions from UC leaders, pending corrections	Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS) August Betzler (i2CAT), Adrián Pino Martínez (i2CAT), Nikos Athanasopoulos (CAPT), Anargyros Roumeliotis (ICCS), Annika Tuulemäe (CAFA), Simonas Audickas (ART21), Justė Vežikuskaitė (ART21), Martynas Velička (BENCO), Jérémie Haumont (EVILVO)
V0.95	17/11/2023	95	UC leaders corrections & peer review feedback	August Betzler (i2CAT), Adrián Pino Martínez (i2CAT), Nikos Athanasopoulos (CAPT), Anargyros Roumeliotis (ICCS), Annika Tuulemäe (CAFA), Simonas Audickas (ART21), Justė Vežikuskaitė (ART21), Martynas Velička (BENCO), Jérémie Haumont (EVILVO)
V0.96	24/11/23	96	Review from PC and TM	Eirini Liotou (ICCS), Anargyros Roumeliotis (ICCS), August Betzler (i2CAT),
V1.0	29/11/23	100	All review comments addressed & integrated	Panayiotis Klitou (eBOS)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
CAPEX	Capital expenses
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
E2E	End-to-end
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KFT	Knowledge Facilitation Tool
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Labs
OPEX	Operating expenses
PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case

1 Executive Summary

Deliverable *D5.1 - Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report (1st version)* is part of Work Package 5 - Technology Validation and Impact Assessment of the XGain project, and addresses Task 5.1 - Setup Scene, Trials Definition and Operational Management. It is the first version of three deliverables, also released in M26 (D5.2) and M35 (D5.3).

The purpose of this deliverable is to set up the procedures for the implementation of the six Use Cases (UCs), and a detailed testing and operational management plan for the validation procedures in the field trials, which will be continuously updated and reported at the end of each testing and validation phase. The deliverable will define the framework setup for the implementation of the UCs, during the planning phase. This includes defining baseline conditions, relevant assumptions, as well as quantifiable metrics and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Additionally, it encompasses the validation methodology, the planning and oversight of activities, and the ensuing learning process, all of which are accompanied by recommendations and best practices. These procedures were meticulously crafted and approved by all project partners before actual implementation to assess the feasibility and practicality of the UC validation and optimize their efficiency.

The report provides an overview of the overall context and offers comprehensive information about the present physical setup, integration, and preparatory actions and activities in the operational environments of the six UCs, specifying the order in which these activities will occur to attain their intended targets. It defines the different testing and validation levels, including the end-to-end (E2E) field trial testing of the technology mixtures (connectivity and edge processing technologies) developed under WP3, the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT) and output suggestions, including the proposition of innovative business models, as developed in WP4, and the overall social acceptance and impact assessment of the XGain solutions in the 6 UCs, taking into consideration technological, economic, social and environmental indicators.

The field trials will be following the Deming Plan – Do – Check – Act (PDCA) cycle. There will be a constant interplay between the UC validations' progress and the research developments, as explained in the report. The PDCA is a valuable tool and a fundamental component of agile methodology, and it is employed to guide the testing and validation of XGain solutions in a controlled manner. The work undertaken in T5.1 and presented in this deliverable, builds upon the work previously carried out in WP2 and specifically refines and develops the initial planning from T2.3. WP5 also oversees and synchronizes the planning and the anticipated activities in conjunction with WP2-4 to ensure alignment with the project's objectives. The deliverable presents and explains the interplay with WP3-4 in order to fine-tune the developments of those WPs, outlining key tasks and responsibilities, and the various interactions within this process.

The procedure outlined in this Deliverable will persist throughout the project's duration, with ongoing monitoring of all UC activities, including their implementation, deployment, and testing. This oversight will occur in conjunction with the forthcoming revised Deliverables, D5.2 and D5.3.

2 Introduction

The XGain project aims to offer smart XG, last-mile connectivity, and edge computing solutions to key stakeholders, including municipalities, policymakers, farmers, foresters, and their respective associations. The project's primary goal is to develop a Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT). This tool will support these stakeholders in crafting and assessing business models and making well-informed choices regarding technology ecosystems. These choices are intended to enhance the overall resilience and energy efficiency of their regions, play a role in mitigating the effects of climate change, and diminish digital disparities among various demographic groups.

The developed technologies will undergo validation in six distinct field trials conducted across diverse landscapes in Europe, encompassing a broad spectrum of services and regions/communities. These trials will be conducted in 6 different Use Cases (UCs), at the following levels and in corresponding locations:

- **UC1: Rural Community Services** in Spain (community level)
- **UC2: eHealth** in Greece (regional level)
- **UC3: Remote Community** in the UK (on an island)
- **UC4: Farming and Forestry** in Lithuania (at the farm and community levels)
- **UC5: Aquaculture** in Croatia (at the farm and community levels)
- **UC6: Livestock and Agriculture** in Belgium (at the farm and community levels)

WP5 will validate the different technologies, the developed business models and the XGain KFT through testing procedures and field trials.

Deliverable D5.1 - Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report (1st version) represents the initial version in a sequence of deliverables bearing the same title, designed to address the activities initially undertaken in T5.1, focusing on setting the stage for field trials and defining their operational management over the period from Month 12 to Month 35 of the project. The primary objectives of D5.1 are to develop a comprehensive testing plan with a strong emphasis on meeting stringent KPI requirements vital for the successful delivery of social innovation and citizen engagement. The objectives of this first version are essentially to set-up the plan, processes and the monitoring of the UCs progress and implementation. It details the six UCs and the methodology selection of using the PDCA model in managing, planning and monitoring this achievement and its progression. It also encompasses the methodologies for preparation of result evaluations, including behavioural indicators for baseline conditions, relevant assumptions, workflows, checklists, templates, reference/target KPIs, and key roles and interactions within the process.

2.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map XGain Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

D5.1 Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report (1st version)

Initial (A) version including the planning and setup handbook

TASKS			
Task 5.1: Setup Scene, Trials Definition and Operational Management	Detailed testing plan, ensuring the stringent KPI requirements needed for the successful delivery of innovative social innovation and citizen engagement, providing in further details, and refining, the initial planning developed in T2.3.	Testing plan: Chapters 4 &5 KPI definition: Chapters 6.5, 7.5, 8.5, 9.5, 10.5, 11.5	The detailed testing plan and operational management strategy is outlined in Chapters 4 &5. UC-specific KPIs are documented in Chapter 6-11.
	This phase will focus on defining a proof of concept that will use XGain technologies in real conditions, through the development of a proper test strategy to adjust depth and coverage of testing to available resources and target stakeholders.	Chapters 4 &5	Validation strategy and stakeholder involvement.
	The process in developing the use case validation will be agile, so that a constant interaction cycle of progress will be delivering the results incrementally as services. To this end, the field trials will be following the Deming Plan – Do – Check – Act cycle. There will be a constant interplay between the use case validations’ progress and the research developments.	Chapter 5	Agile methodology, PDCA cycle and monitoring system explain in Chapter 5.
	Preparation of the evaluation of the results, including behavioural indications on the baseline conditions, relevant assumptions to	Chapter 6 to 11	UC-specific planning including KPIs, procedures, dataset

<p>be considered (if any), workflow, checklists and templates, reference/target KPIs to be met/benchmarked, and key roles and interactions within this process. This task will also allow the project staff to take stock of relevant data, define datasets for impact analysis, process collect measurements, and organise outcomes into actionable information. The results generated will be compared to the reference target KPIs to assess the performance of the system, provide feedback for refinements and, eventually, final recommendations, which will be fed to T5.8.</p>		<p>description, key roles, assumptions and risks, included in the UC-specific Chapters 6-11.</p>
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Chapter 1 – Executive Summary

Chapter 2 – Introduction: General information on the work and mapping of XGain outputs in deliverable

Chapter 3 – WP5 overview and objectives: Gives an overview of the different tasks, activities, and objectives within WP5, the partners responsible for the various activities in the validation work, related WPs, tasks and deliverables that have provided input to this deliverable and WP5 in general, and tasks that take as input the output of WP5. Furthermore, an elaborate analysis of the WP5 objectives is presented, which forms the basis for the development of the testing and validation plan.

Chapter 4 – Demonstration of the XGain Testing and Validation plan: The different “layers” of testing and validation are presented, and tools, procedures and guidelines for the validation of each are documented.

Chapter 5 – Planning and set-up of the XGain UCs: The section describes how the UCs will align with the proposed testing plan (outputs in Chapters 6-11), and demonstrates the managing and monitoring system of the plan, with particular emphasis on the Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle methodology.

Chapters 6-11 – Use Case-specific chapters that give an overview of the UC and setup, and align with the proposed testing and validation plan. Key roles and interactions, implementation plans, test scenarios, data definition, challenges, risks, assumptions, and KPIs for the validation of technologies, and impact assessment are documented per UC in these chapters.

Chapter 12 – Conclusions

3 WP5 Overview and Objectives

This section provides a brief overview of WP5 and its goals, serving as a basis for this report. It includes details about the activities and task distribution within WP5, with a specific focus on T5.1.

3.1 WP5 Overview

WP5, led by eBOS and encompassing eight distinct tasks, is dedicated to the validation of various technologies, developed business models, and the XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool through rigorous testing procedures and real-world field trials. Within this context, WP5's core objectives are multi-faceted. It seeks to facilitate comprehensive planning, setup, and operational management to enable advanced validation within real-life UCs, ultimately confirming the technological proficiency of the developed business models and the XGain tool. This involves validating the common objectives of the UC validations, as outlined in Section 1.2.3. of the Grant Agreement. Furthermore, WP5 aims to evaluate the project's outcomes through performance assessment and a commercial readiness evaluation. It will actively monitor regulatory developments at regional, national, and European levels to ensure that the proposed demonstrations adhere to the regulatory framework while also proposing recommendations for enhancing social acceptance and pertinent regulatory aspects. WP5 will engage with a wide range of end-users, relevant initiatives, and existing tools, resulting in the enhancement of the XGain tool's functionalities. Additionally, it will explore avenues for demonstrating interoperability and scalability.

Task 5.1: Setup Scene, Trials Definition and Operational Management - focuses on creating a robust testing plan with strict KPI requirements to ensure the success of social innovation and citizen engagement. This includes refining initial planning from T2.3 and building a proof of concept using XGain technologies in real-world scenarios. An agile approach allows for continuous progress as services evolve. Field trials follow the Deming Plan – Do – Check – Act cycle, maintaining an ongoing connection between UC validation and research developments. The task also involves preparing result evaluations, including behavioural indicators, assumptions, checklists, and templates, as well as defining datasets for impact analysis. Results are compared to reference KPIs to assess system performance and provide feedback for improvements, feeding into T5.8. This deliverable D5.1 reflects the work carried out in T5.1 during months 12 to 15.

Tasks 5.2 - 5.7: XGain Use Case Execution - concentrate on executing and implementing six distinct real-life XGain use cases in diverse geographical locations and sectors. The primary goal is to showcase the capabilities of XGain's developed technological solutions, business models, and KFT. A standardized approach will be applied across all UCs, including defining testing procedures based on the outcomes from T5.1, preparing the test site and infrastructure support, onboarding services and applications developed in WP4, configuring and testing the required technologies for each UC, executing the testing procedures, and analyzing the results. Feedback will be provided to various project components, including T4.4 for user experience, T5.8 for social acceptance and impact, and T6.1 for public engagement.

Task 5.8: Social Acceptance, Performance Evaluation, Impact Analysis and Replication Guidelines - conducts a comprehensive evaluation of XGain's technological, social, economic, and environmental impacts. Its objective is to provide detailed guidelines for applying XGain technological solutions and the KFT in practical real-world scenarios. This encompasses social acceptance assessment, performance evaluation of technological solutions, and energy efficiency validation. By consolidating data from various project sites, it extracts meaningful insights, generalizes findings, and offers concrete recommendations for best practices. It goes beyond

technology assessment to perform an in-depth Impact Analysis, considering socio-economic and environmental aspects at different levels of granularity. The task ultimately yields Deliverable D5.4, complete with guidelines for adapting the decision support tool in diverse environments, documenting best practices, and promoting community inclusiveness and development.

The interdependencies between WP5 tasks (flow of inputs and outputs between tasks) are further discussed in Section 3.4 and shown in Figure 2.

Deliverables produced in WP5 are as follows:

D5.1 – Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report (1st version) [M15]: This deliverable provides the initial testing plan, UC planning and setup handbook.

D5.2 – Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report (2nd version) [M26]: This second version outlines the XGain tool testing and technology validation for all the use cases including feedback, and any necessary updates to the testing plan.

D5.3 – Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report (3rd version) [M35]: Final version presenting the XGain tool validation and field trial results of the 6 unique use cases.

D5.4 – Performance evaluation, impact assessment and replication guidelines [M35]: Final report on the performance evaluation and impact analysis, as well as replication guidelines received from users.

3.2 XGain Objectives associated to WP5

The section below presents the objectives associated to WP5, as taken from the Grant Agreement, and a further analysis of those. These objectives and goals were considered in order to formulate the testing and validation strategy, as well as identify the different levels of validation which are presented later in the report.

From **Project Objective #4: To validate the outcome of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool in 6 unique fields with different technical, environmental, societal and economical structures and needs**, it is stated that:

“XGain project aims to propose an ecosystem of technological solutions for connectivity and edge processing in parallel with innovative business models. The technologies are developed and validated in i) dry-run testing in lab environment to validate the XGain tool technological recommendations and receive feedback for further updates, and ii) 6 unique field trials in multi-actor landscapes across Europe, covering an appropriate range of services and regions/communities, namely: Rural Community Services-Spain-community level, eHealth-Greece-regional level, Remote Community-UK-island, Farming and Forestry-Lithuania-farm and community levels, Aquaculture-Croatia-farm and community levels, and Livestock and Agriculture-Belgium-farm and community levels.”

This objective extract refers to the testing of the technological solutions for connectivity and edge processing developed in WP3. The technologies will first be validated in dry-run testing in laboratory environment, and this is part of Task 3.4, which is currently ongoing. Further details regarding the dry-run testing of technologies will not be discussed in this deliverable but are instead provided in D3.3.

The focus of WP5 testing of the technological solutions will be put in the E2E testing in the field trials of the 6 UCs. The E2E testing of technologies involves the testing of the integrated segments of connectivity and edge processing enablers. Connectivity is a cornerstone of the XGain project, and the core of the KFT. Testing the various connectivity solutions is crucial to validate their reliability, coverage, and suitability for different UCs.

Testing should involve assessing the performance of each connectivity solution under real-world conditions in each UC. Edge processing is essential for ensuring real-time data processing and decision-making in various applications. This involves testing the edge processing components of the XGain ecosystem in each UC. It may include benchmarking latency, computing power, and the ability to support different data processing algorithms at the edge.

The six unique field trials at the six UCs encompass a broad range of unique sectors and services. XGain aims to address a broad range of services and regions/communities, each with unique requirements and characteristics. Testing across diverse scenarios ensures that the proposed solutions are adaptable and versatile. Furthermore, multi-actor landscapes bring together various stakeholders, including citizens, local authorities, businesses, and more. Testing in such complex environments ensures that the XGain solutions can accommodate diverse interests and needs.

With regards to the testing and validation of the KFT output, **Objective #4** further states:

“In parallel, the technological solutions are acting as a knowledge base for the system aiming to fine tune them through the outcome of the usage of the XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool.”

These objectives and requirements refer to the validation and testing of the KFT outputs. The KFT should undergo rigorous testing and validation in the 6 different Living Labs, each representing a unique field or scenario. The outcomes of these validations will serve as feedback for fine-tuning the KFT. The output suggestions of the KFT are based on assessment models developed in other WPs of the project. Under WP3, the technology mix finder and dimensioning solver models were developed, to identify the most appropriate solutions based on sector and service selection, area specification, and user service requirements. Under WP4, the techno-economic assessment model was developed in T4.1, the socio-environmental assessment model in T4.2, and business-model propositions in T4.3, while T4.4 developed the human-machine interface (dashboard) of the KFT and integration of the various models. The outcome of the KFT testing and validation will, therefore, be fed into those WPs and tasks in an iterative manner, to make refinements and fine-tune these models.

With regards to the business models, **Objective 3** of the project states:

“During the use cases, the business models will be validated in real-life conditions and fine-tuned to be implemented under full market terms and further optimise the dynamic selection.”

The validation of business models is crucial to ensure that the proposed models are not just theoretical concepts but are practical and effective in real-world situations. It helps in aligning business models with the specific needs and challenges of each UC, ensuring that they are suitable for various industries and sectors. Real-life validation provides insights into how these models perform under different conditions, allowing for necessary adjustments and optimizations.

Through the validation process, the business models may require adjustments and fine-tuning. This ensures that they are ready to be implemented under full market terms. The business models should be capable of dynamic selection, meaning they can adapt to changing conditions and user requirements. This adaptability allows for continuous optimization based on real-world feedback and market trends.

Lastly, **Objective #4** also states that:

“Strong involvement of citizen associations as well as local authorities will be targeted in order to assess the social acceptance of the recommended solutions, including technological, environmental and business model aspects.”

And, also, from the **Grant Agreement Section 2.3 Summary**, it is required that:

- The Knowledge Facilitation Tool is validated in 6 LLs and promoted in 10 DIHs and 40 Associations
- The Knowledge Facilitation Tool is validated with at least 600 users in 6 different areas/Regions

The KFT should be tested and validated by a substantial number of users (a minimum of 600) in these 6 different areas or regions. The reason for involving a significant number of users is to gather diverse feedback and assess the tool's usability, effectiveness, and adaptability from various perspectives.

Beyond validation, the KFT should also be promoted to ensure its adoption and usage. This involves dissemination to 10 Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and 40 Associations. The objective is to make the KFT known and accessible to a broader audience, including businesses, organizations, and communities. Strong involvement of citizen associations and local authorities in the promotion aims to assess the social acceptance of the KFT.

"Social acceptance" refers to the level of approval and willingness of the community or society at large to embrace and use a particular technology, solution, or innovation. It goes beyond mere technological acceptance, and encompasses broader aspects such as the social, environmental, and ethical implications of a solution. In the XGain project, involving citizen associations and local authorities ensures that the perspectives and concerns of the local community are considered in the implementation of the technological solutions. Social acceptance is closely tied to the long-term sustainability of technological solutions. Solutions that are accepted by the community are more likely to be sustainable because they have the support of the local population.

3.3 WP5 Activities and Task Allocation

Under the WP5 - Technology Validation and Impact Assessment, **eBOS** as the **WP5 leader** and leader of T5.1 - Setup Scene, Trials Definition and Operational Management, is responsible for the overall coordination and management of WP5, ensuring that the objectives and tasks are carried out efficiently. eBOS is responsible to perform the relevant planning, set-up and operational management in order to validate the technological performance of the developed business models and XGain tool. eBOS will also oversee the work of the UC Leaders and other team members involved in WP5, ensuring that everyone is aligned with the WP5 goals and objectives.

Use Case Leaders are responsible for specific UCs within the project. UC leaders lead and manage the activities related to their designated UC. UC leaders play a crucial role in the validation process, ensuring that the solutions are tested in real-world conditions and meet the predefined KPIs. They are directly involved in planning and executing field trials within their UC area. This may involve working with local communities, setting KPIs and test scenarios, testing technologies, and collecting data. UC Leader, with the support of UC Technical Leaders, are responsible for the set-up and implementation of the technologies in their UC. They oversee the collection of data and information related to their UC, ensuring that it aligns with the goals and objectives. They are also responsible to engage with local stakeholders, such as citizen associations and local

authorities, to assess social acceptance and gather feedback on the solutions. Ultimately, they should provide regular progress reports to the WP leader and the project consortium, sharing insights and outcomes from their specific UC.

The role of each **Use Case Technical Leader**, is to provide technical support to the UC leader based on their technical expertise in their respective domains. In cooperation with the UC leader, UC technical leaders will contribute to the definition of technical KPIs and testing procedures and oversee the implementation of the technological solutions within the UC.

Lastly, **ICCS** is responsible for the social acceptance, performance evaluation, impact analysis and replication guidelines conducted within WP5. ICCS will perform a comprehensive evaluation of XGain's technological, social, economic, and environmental impacts to provide detailed guidelines for applying XGain solutions and the KFT in practical real-world scenarios.

The above information is summarised in Figure 1, also indicating the partners allocated as UC leaders and UC technical leaders.

Figure 1: WP5 structure, activities, and responsible partners

3.4 Related WPs, Tasks and Deliverables

In this section the interdependencies between WP5 tasks, and other relevant WPs, tasks and deliverables are presented. These relationships are vital to comprehend, in order to build a robust testing and validation plan, as well as to follow an iterative methodology to use the results from the field trials to fine-tune the models, developed technologies, and the KFT.

The detailed testing plan and trials definition developed in T5.1 will take as input work developed previously in other WPs and tasks, as discussed below.

- WP2 – Interactive Definition of User-oriented Requirements:

From **WP2, T2.1** (Stakeholder Mapping and End-user Needs Analysis through Processes of Co-creation), the stakeholder mapping led to the identification of the stakeholders and end-users of the KFT in each of the 6 UC locations, as included in **D2.1**. Stakeholders participated in the co-creation workshops organised by T2.1 in order to collect user requirements. These stakeholders will be invited to join the workshops organised in the 6 UCs, where demonstration of the XGain solutions will take place, and be involved in the validation of the tool, providing feedback which can be used for the social acceptance assessment, business model validation and impact assessment. **T2.2** (Ensuring a Fair Social, Digital, Environmental and Economic Transition) plays a critical role in addressing social acceptance through inclusiveness, social exclusion analyses, and co-design efforts. The findings and approaches developed in Task 2.2 and **D2.2** provide valuable insights and methodologies that are applied to the validation and testing strategies in WP5, ensuring that the project's technological solutions are socially accepted and accessible to all stakeholders, contributing to a fair and equitable transition. The stakeholder readiness to adopt new technologies and readiness level analysis for transition pathways will play an important role in the social acceptance analysis in WP5. **T2.3** (XGain Use Case Requirements and Specifications for Connectivity and Edge Technology Enablers) has specified the functional and non-functional stakeholder requirements for the overall XGain propositions, and has defined the operational environment and service level specificities of each UC. Furthermore, KPIs related to the technical performance evaluation of the proposed solutions have been identified in T2.3. The testing plan is based on this initial planning performed in T2.3, as described in **D2.3**. **T2.4** (XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool Architecture Design and Technical Specifications) provides the functional and non-functional requirements and architecture, in **D2.4**, upon which the KFT was designed in WP4. These requirements will form the basis of part of the testing of the KFT, to assess whether it delivers and performs as expected.

- WP3 – XGain Connectivity and Edge Technology Enablers

In **WP3, T3.4** delves into the dry-run laboratory testing of the developed technology mixtures. A detailed assessment methodology of the last mile connectivity, edge processing solutions, and their mixture (E2E testing) is developed and tested in the laboratory, and suitable technical KPIs and performance criteria are specified. In **D3.3**, “isolated” measurements about technical KPIs for different last mile connectivity technologies and edge processing solutions in laboratory environments are provided. The UC-specific performance criteria for the testing of the technologies are taken by WP5 and further extended to include KPIs for the on-site testing of technologies.

- WP4 – XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool Development

The interplay between **WP4** and WP5 is vital, as the feedback collected from testing and validation will be fed into WP4 to fine-tune the assessment models and design of the KFT. There will be a constant interplay between the UC validations’ progress and the research developments. Feedback concerning the user experience of the KFT will be fed to T4.4 for improvements. Regarding the business models, feedback from the real-life conditions’ validations will be used to fine-tune them and make them capable of being implemented under full market terms and further optimise the dynamic selection.

- WP5 – Technology Validation and Impact Assessment

Within **WP5, T5.1** develops the testing and validation plan (presented in this deliverable **D5.1**) which is delivered to **T5.2-T5.7** for the execution and implementation of the 6 real-life UCs. The field trials will be following the Deming Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle, meaning that a constant monitoring and evaluation of the field trial results will be compared to the objectives and expectations from the UCs, and this will be used to identify

necessary corrections to the testing plan, in order to align with the scope and goal of testing. The testing plan in T5.1 will thus be updated accordingly and presented in **D5.2** and **D5.3**. Also, in these two deliverables results from the field trials execution will also be reported. The outputs of tasks T5.1, and T5.2-T5.7, will be fed into **T5.8** in order to perform the social acceptance assessment, performance evaluation, and impact analysis. These evaluations will be presented in **D5.4**.

- WP6 – Impact Maximisation and Outreach

The interactions between WP5 and **WP6** will involve providing feedback from the field trials execution to **T6.1** regarding public engagement. Furthermore, **T6.2** (Standardisation and interaction with policy-makers, associations, and other related projects) will provide a list of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and association, to whom the KFT will be promoted, and these DIHs and associations will form part of the mixed approach in the process of gathering feedback for the KFT and XGain solutions in general, to aid in the social acceptance evaluation. The social acceptance and impact analysis developed in T5.8 will also be used in **T6.4** (Social policy innovation, data management and IPR activities) in policy co-creation activities and will result in the formulation of concrete policy recommendations.

All of the above information is summarised and illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Interdependencies within and between WP5 and other WPs

4 Demonstration of the XGain Testing and Validation Plan

The successful execution of the XGain project hinges on rigorous testing and validation processes to ensure that the proposed technological solutions and innovations effectively address the project's core objectives. This Testing and Validation Plan serves as a foundational document that outlines the systematic approach and methodologies for verifying the project's key components, in order to have common procedures and a unified approach to be followed by all UCs, and common reference points.

4.1 Testing and validation “layers”

The scope of this Testing and Validation Plan encompasses a range of activities, from the evaluation of technological performance in diverse UCs to the assessment of social acceptance and environmental impacts. It takes into account the fine-tuning of business models for sustainable, market-ready solutions, and leverages the knowledge base created through the project's innovations. It elaborates on the strategies, methodologies, and KPIs that will govern the testing and validation processes across the various UCs. By adhering to this plan, the XGain project aims to deliver on its promise of fostering technological advancements, facilitating knowledge, and driving positive transformations in the communities and regions it serves.

The first step into formulating a sound and rigorous testing plan was to collect and analyse the objectives related to testing and validation and WP5, as described in Section 3.2 of this report. The testing and validation plan proposed is based on those objectives, and primarily requires the identification of the different “layers” or aspects of the XGain project’s outputs that need to be validated, and subsequent development of methodologies, tools and timelines for the validation procedures. Careful consideration of the relevant objectives and analysis has led to the identification of the following testing and validation layers, as shown below, and further discussed in the following sections.

A. Testing of technological solutions in the field

B. KFT testing

C. Social Acceptance and Impact Assessment

4.1.1 Testing of technological solutions in the field

The heart of the XGain project lies in its commitment to delivering tangible and innovative technological solutions for connectivity and edge processing. Project Objective 4, as discussed in Section 3.2, explicitly states the necessity of validating these technological solutions in six distinct UCs, each representing a unique field with different technical, environmental, societal, and economic structures and needs.

The primary goal is to ensure that the technological solutions developed within the project can be effectively applied to real-world scenarios. This aligns with the overarching project aim to create a practical ecosystem of technological solutions that address the diverse needs of European communities and regions. By conducting field trials, we can fine-tune the technological solutions to cater to the specific needs of each case, enhancing their suitability for widespread adoption.

Testing of the developed technological solutions, or technology mixture, comprising connectivity and edge processing enablers, at a first stage will take place in the laboratory. This is part of T3.4 and the work done

related to this is presented in D3.3 (for “isolated” measurements of connectivity, and edge processing enablers) and in D3.4 (for an integrated E2E testing of the solutions). This work is not part of the field trials execution; however, it forms a prerequisite as many technological KPIs and target values will be identified, which will be then extended and used in the field trials testing.

The testing of technological solutions in the field trials is divided into three phases, as described below.

Preparation and set-up phase [M12-M15]: This phase involves setting up the field trials in each of the six UCs. It includes defining the field trial objectives, identifying the resources required, test scenarios, KPIs, any challenges, risks, or assumptions, and establishing a clear plan for execution. This plan is flexible to be modified accordingly along the duration of the execution of the tests if needed, in order to align with the expected outcomes. The output from this preparation and planning phase for each UC is presented in Chapters 6 to 11 of this report.

Phase 1 [M16-M26]: In this phase, the XGain ecosystem of technologies will be finalised, and the selected combination of the technologies, connectivity and edge processing enablers, for each UC will be tested (E2E testing) in the real-world field conditions. The purpose of this testing is to assess how well these technologies perform under practical conditions and to identify any issues or areas for improvement.

Phase 2 [M27-M36]: In this phase, the project aims to reach Technology Readiness Level 6 (TRL6) of the developed solutions. TRL6 represents a level of technology maturity where the system is considered a prototype or pilot system, and it is tested in an operational environment, i.e., the technologies will be rigorously tested, refined, and demonstrated in the actual settings where they are intended to be used. The implementation and validation activities will be conducted using an iterative and incremental approach. This approach will involve continuous refinement and improvement based on feedback and learning. The results of these field tests will provide the basis for making informed decisions, sharing information, operating the technologies effectively, facilitating learning, and driving further improvement.

For the purpose of E2E testing of the technology mixture, during the preparation phase, each UC had to identify appropriate technological KPIs, target values, calculation methods and validation methods, to assess the performance of those technologies in the field. For this process, the template tables and guidelines were provided to the UC leaders, as shown in Table 2. It should be noted that the technological KPIs selected by UC leaders in each UC (Chapters 6 to 11) and the information provided for each KPI is a tentative selection that will guide the testing and validation work, and is based on the current knowledge and information that the UC leaders have. A more precise definition of these KPIs will be done in real-time, onsite, where the exact setting will be fully known and indicators will be monitored accordingly.

Table 2: Template table for definition of technological KPIs for E2E technology mix testing in field trials

KPI	Target value	Actual value	Calculation method	Validation method
<i>Technological metric related to E2E performance testing of technology mix e.g., Network Reliability</i>	<i>Expected value-reference point for success e.g., 99.90%</i>	<i>Actual value measured from testing in the field e.g., 99.95%</i>	<i>Method to measure KPI, or derive from collected data e.g., Measure the uptime and reliability of the 5G network infrastructure, ensuring uninterrupted</i>	<i>Methodology to validate KPI – how the actual value compares to target value e.g., Keep the UE connected during 24h, while using a ping to keep the</i>

			<i>drone operations</i>	<i>connection alive.</i>
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Further to the definition of technological KPIs, the UC leaders have made an initial attempt to identify test scenarios for the testing of the technology mixtures. These test scenarios relate to the specific services that each UC is addressing, and represent a real application for the specific use of the technology mix and user equipment. The template for test scenarios identification, and an indicative example, is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Test scenarios template for testing of technologies in field trials

XGain UC - Service	<i>E.g., UC3: Remote Community (UK) – Precision Agriculture</i>		
Scenario 1	<i>E.g., Taking soil humidity measurements with a robot</i>		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
<i>Equipment to use & parameters to measure and how E.g., The robot drives to the field and inserts sensors 20-25 cm deep into the soil. The mobile robot will measure the ground, recording GPS coordinates, timestamps, and measurement IDs at the same time.</i>	<i>E.g., the data on soil humidity will be collected and recorded accurately.</i>	<i>TBC after measurement</i>	<i>Any other relevant information e.g., Near real time data from the field also reduces the amount of irrigation water.</i>

4.1.2 KFT Testing

The importance of testing and validating the KFT and its outputs in real-life conditions aligns with Objective 4. It ensures that the KFT performs seamlessly and effectively while enhancing knowledge sharing, promoting technological solutions, and driving sustainable business models. The validation of the KFT plays a pivotal role in the fine-tuning the technological solutions finder and dimensioning solver models (WP3), as well as the techno-economic (T4.1) and socio-environmental models (T4.2), and the business models (T4.3), as well as the user experience (T4.4).

4.1.2.1 KFT Functionality Validation

The architecture and design of the KFT was based upon several functional and non-functional requirements, many of which were collected from stakeholders (T2.1), and the architecture was developed in T2.4. The KFT was designed based on these requirements, and the KFT validation will be achieved by considering the 6 UCs and assessing to what extent the KFT can meet the UC needs. In Chapters 6-11, the section “Mapping of UC with KFT functionalities” describes the relationship between the specific needs of each UC and the corresponding features of the KFT, i.e., how the functionalities and capabilities of the KFT are aligned and tailored to meet the specific UC demands. The KFT was strategically designed and integrated into each UC to ensure that it addresses the objectives of each UC.

For the validation purposes, an approach similar to the test scenarios described above will be followed, but this will be specific for the testing of the performance of the KFT, rather than the technological solutions. Several test scenarios that relate to the needs of the 6 UCs will be identified, also mapping those to specific functional/non-functional requirements as described in T2.3. The corresponding sectors and services and location details describing the location of each UC, and service requirements of each UC, will be chosen as input parameters for the KFT and the expected result will be logged. The KFT will be run with those parameters and the actual KFT output will be used to assess to what extent the KFT performs and delivers as required. The template table to be used for the test scenarios identification, and an indicative example, is presented in Table 4. This testing will be performed in Phase 1 of the WP5 timeline (Section 4.2). Currently the first version of the KFT is under development. The UC leaders will be able to identify these test scenarios once the first KFT version is released and the exact features of the tool are known to the UC leaders.

Table 4: Test scenarios template for testing of KFT against requirements

XGain UC - Service	<i>E.g., UC3: Remote Community (UK) – Precision Agriculture</i>		
Scenario 1	<i>E.g., A farm wants to install soil humidity sensors to be taking real-time measurements and optimise watering. They are interested in the most economic solution.</i>		
Requirement Reference	<i>E.g., FR14 - The KFT needs to visualize CAPEX/OPEX, quantity/number and type of infrastructure elements, specific technologies suggested, and other quantitative information about the suggested technology mix in a table or summary</i>		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
<i>E.g., The KFT is launched. Agriculture (sector) and precision agriculture (service) are chosen. The area specification for the farm is provided (weather, terrain, area size etc). The service requirements are provided (IoT sensors, real time monitoring). Impact weight on most economical solution is chosen.</i>	<i>E.g., KFT suggests most appropriate technology mixtures (connectivity and edge computing enablers), and numbers of infrastructure elements, with CAPEX and OPEX information presented in a table, per element.</i>	<i>TBC after running the test</i>	

Furthermore, the KFT will be validated with at least “600 users in 6 different areas/regions and 6 LLs” (corresponding to the locations of the 6 UCs), and “promoted in 10 DIHs and 40 Associations”, as required by the Grant Agreement. A mixed approach will be followed for this type of validation. It will involve different target groups – stakeholders invited to the UC workshops, DIHs, members of associations identified in each UC, and will be achieved through a combination of communication channels.

During the field trials execution, the UCs will organise on-site workshops where invited stakeholders (already identified in T2.1 and through an ongoing identification and engagement process) will have the opportunity to watch demonstrations of the implemented technological solutions, and furthermore, will have the chance to use the KFT and provide feedback to the UC leaders. Feedback can be in the form of oral communication - the stakeholders can express their opinions more precisely for specific aspects of the KFT, or through a questionnaire/survey that will assess the overall performance of the tool. Furthermore, the KFT can be promoted to DIHs and associations, where participating members will have the opportunity to use the tool and provide feedback through an online survey.

The feedback received from these activities will be integrated into appropriate tasks in WP3 and WP4, in order to fine-tune the models, and improve the tool's usability based on the received users' experience. These activities are expected to span both Phase 1 and Phase 2 of the WP5 time plan, as they should align with engagement of stakeholders and organisation of the workshops in the UCs, and finalisation of the technological solutions. UC leaders will have the flexibility to decide exact dates for the workshops based on the progress of testing and validation of solutions, and readiness of demonstrations. As a final remark, the KFT validation work transcends mere technical verification, as it extends to social acceptance and environmental sustainability assessment, discussed in Section 4.1.3.

4.1.2.2 Business Models Validation

As the Business Models are an output produced from the KFT and developed in Task 4.3, we consider this validation to be part of the KFT output validation. One of the main functionalities of the KFT is to *"identify business models for the operation of last mile connectivity and edge processing solutions"*. There is an agreement for the operation of at least one business model in each of the LLs. During the UC implementation, the business models will be validated in real-life conditions and fine-tuned to be implemented under full market terms and further optimise the dynamic selection. The feedback collected from the UC will be incorporated into T4.3 to come up with the final business models.

The validation plan for the Business Model foresees 6 training days for the adoption of the innovative business models, which can take place during the organised UCs workshops, targeting farmers, foresters and rural communities, and showcasing pathways towards the most efficient utilisation of the business models. Feedback provided during the training days and workshops from the attending stakeholders will constitute one of the many sources of input for the refinement and fine-tuning of the business models. Feedback from UC leaders who are running the UC and operate specific business models will also be used for this purpose.

Lastly, Objective 4 mentions that strong involvement of citizen associations as well as local authorities will be targeted in order to assess model aspects. These will provide real-world insights, market feedback, and a deep understanding of local needs and conditions. Their active participation in the validation process helps ensure that the business models are not only technically sound but also well-suited for the specific target groups and services that they want to address.

4.1.3 Social Acceptance and Impact Assessment

Further to the technological testing of the developed technology mixtures, the testing and validation of the KFT as a tool, and its outputs, the work in WP5 requires the assessment of social acceptance of the recommended solutions, including technological, environmental and business model aspects. Analysis and evaluation of the project's outcomes through performance evaluation, impact analysis and social acceptance assessment will

form the basis for deliverable D5.4, and relevant work including KPIs definition, engagement of relevant stakeholders, and methodologies need to be defined in the planning stage.

Assessing social acceptance ensures that the project's technological solutions are not only technically feasible but also culturally, ethically, and environmentally acceptable to the communities they are intended to serve. This approach enhances the likelihood of successful implementation and long-term sustainability. For the purpose of social acceptance, a mixed approach will be followed to engage and draw feedback from a range of target groups: Stakeholders and end users invited to workshops, local authorities, citizen associations, DIHs. The mixed approach to measure social acceptance will involve the following steps:

- **Engagement and Dialogue:** Establish communication channels with citizen associations and local authorities to understand their perspectives.
- **Conduct Surveys and Interviews:** Gather feedback through online surveys and interviews to collect data on social acceptance. Questions can be designed to cover technological, environmental, social and business model aspects.
- **Workshops:** Workshops will be organised by each UC leader to demonstrate the XGain solutions and collect feedback on the solutions, KFT outputs and business models.
- **Impact Assessment:** Evaluate the potential technological, economic, social, and environmental impacts of the implemented solutions.

Strong involvement of **citizen associations** and **DIHs** will help in assessing social acceptance. DIHs often have strong networks and connections within their local communities. They can provide valuable insights into the social, economic, and cultural dynamics of the regions where XGain solutions are being deployed. DIHs can serve as intermediaries, helping the XGain project connect with local citizens, businesses, and authorities. They can collect feedback from their members regarding their opinions on the XGain solutions. DIHs can also assist in collecting data related to the impact of XGain solutions on social, economic, and environmental aspects. This data is critical for assessing how well the solutions meet their intended objectives and whether they are positively affecting the community. Identification of citizen associations and DIHs is an ongoing activity initiated as part of T6.2 work, and further supported by UC leaders.

Lastly, an impact assessment evaluation for the implementation of the XGain solutions at each UC will be carried out, as discussed in the following section.

The activities concerning social acceptance assessment will mainly take place in Phase 2 of the WP5 time line, after the solutions are implemented and tested in the LLs.

4.1.3.1 Impact Assessment

In order to evaluate social acceptance of the XGain outputs, an **impact assessment** will be carried out at each UC. This will involve a systematic analysis to evaluate the effects and consequences of the deployment of the XGain solutions, on various domains including technological, economic, social and environmental.

UC leaders are responsible to carry out this impact assessment analysis for the implementation of the proposed technological solutions, and for the specific services that each UC is addressing. In the planning phase, the UC leaders were asked to define **KPIs** for each **impact domain** (technological, economic, social or environmental) and relevant to the service of the UC. The assessment involves defining a **baseline condition** for the specific KPI, that describes the current state of affairs, and is essential for making comparisons before and after the implementation of the XGain solutions. A **calculation method** needs to be defined in order to

collect the necessary data that can be used to derive the KPI value. The **validation method** describes how the predicted value relates to the baseline value, and quantifies the impact on the specific metric. The **predicted value** refers to the predicted condition of the KPI after the implementation of the solution. It is a prediction and not a measured value, as the actual impact may not be obvious or easy to quantify within the short timeframe of the execution of the field trials. For the prediction of those values, feedback collected from stakeholders at the organised workshops, or through surveys and questionnaires from DIHs and associations, can be used. The template tables (Table 5) and guidelines for this assessment methodology were provided to the UC leaders. An initial attempt to provide this information for the impact assessment has been undertaken, and included in Chapters 6 to 11. It should be noted that a tentative selection of indicators has been made, and a more refined selection and information on baseline and predicted values, calculation methods and validation methods will become available after the implementation of the solutions and the start of execution of the field trials. Updates to these tables will be provided in D5.2 and D5.3. Impact assessment is an activity foreseen to take place during Phase 2 of the WP5 timeline.

Table 5: Table template for KPI definition for Impact Assessment analysis

Impact domain (technological, economic, social, environmental)	KPI	Baseline value	Predicted value	Calculation method	Validation method
<i>E.g., Technological</i>	<i>E.g., Soil humidity measurements</i>	<i>E.g., 2 measurements per week</i>	<i>TBC</i>	<i>E.g., How many measurements per week</i>	<i>E.g., Number of measurements to increase by 200-250%</i>
<i>E.g., Economic</i>	<i>E.g., Yield of crops</i>	<i>E.g., 1000 kg/year</i>	<i>TBC</i>	<i>E.g., Yield of crops in kg/month, extrapolated to kg/year</i>	<i>E.g., Yield to increase by 150%</i>
<i>E.g., Social</i>	<i>E.g., Working hours in the field</i>	<i>E.g., 6 hr/day</i>	<i>TBC</i>	<i>E.g., Total working hours for all personnel per day / number of personnel</i>	<i>E.g., Working hours to be reduce by 2-3 hours/day</i>
<i>E.g., Environmental</i>	<i>E.g., Use of pesticides</i>	<i>E.g., 10kg/month</i>	<i>TBC</i>	<i>E.g., Amount of pesticides used in field in kg/month</i>	<i>E.g., Use of pesticides to be reduced by 50%.</i>

4.2 Testing and Validation Timeline

As discussed in previous sections, the timeline for the testing and validation work is divided into three main sections: the Preparation and set-up phase [M12-M15], Phase 1 [M16-M26], and Phase 2 [M27-M36]. The timeline of phases is shown in Figure 3.

The **preparation and set-up phase [M12-M15]** involves preparatory activities, initial planning, setup of UCs and operational management activities. This phase concludes with this deliverable D5.1 – the planning and setup handbook and operational management report, which includes the initial version of the testing plan.

Phase 1 [M16-M26] involves finalisation of the ecosystem of technologies and initial E2E testing of the implemented technologies in the UCs to identify any issues and areas for improvement. The defined technical KPIs and test scenarios will be used in this process. The initial testing of KFT will also take place in this phase. The functionality of the tool will be assessed by comparing the KFT outputs to the expected performance, to evaluate whether it functions as required based on the functional and non-functional requirements. Validation of the business models and collection of feedback from stakeholders, citizen associations, and DIHs for the purposes of social acceptance assessment and fine-tuning of the models and the KFT will also be initiated in this phase and completed in Phase 2.

Phase 2 [M27-M36] will include execution of the field trials, refinements to the technology mixtures, finalisation and demonstration of those. Workshops organised by the UC leaders at the beginning of Phase 2 will engage interested stakeholders for a multi-purpose approach: the implemented technology mixtures will be demonstrated to the stakeholders who will have the opportunity to engage and interact with the technologies; the stakeholders will be trained on the business models, and on the KFT, providing feedback for both (oral, or through questionnaires & surveys), that will be used for validation and social acceptance. UC leaders will communicate the citizen associations and DIHs to promote the KFT and collect feedback (through online surveys) for validation of social acceptance purposes. Impact assessment for the implementation of technologies in each UC will be carried out, based on measurements and feedback collected from the mixed approach throughout the duration of both Phase 1 and 2.

The WP5 timeline presents the activities and events to be undertaken in each of the three different phases of the WP5 duration. However, UC leaders are responsible to generate a more specific implementation timeline adapted to the needs and conditions of their UC. Exact timings and procedures of events, for example the organisation of workshops will be decided by the UC leaders in the planning phase and kept updated along the course of the testing and validation work.

		Lead	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8			
			2024												2025															
			M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36			
WP5	Technology Validation and Impact Assessment	EBOS					MS06											MS08	MS09									MS10		
T5.1	Setup Scene, Trials Definition and Operational Management	EBOS	Preparatory activities, planning, setup of UCs and operational management			D5.1																								
T5.2	Rural Community Services - Spain	I2CAT																D5.2											D5.3	
T5.3	eHealth - Greece	CAP																												
T5.4	Remote Community - UK	CAFA					Phase 1: XGain Tool Testing & Technology Validation												Phase 2: XGain Tool Validation & Field											
T5.5	Farming and Forestry - Lithuania	ART																												
T5.6	Agriculture - Croatia	BENCO																												
T5.7	Livestock and Farming - Belgium	EVILVO																												
T5.8	Social Acceptance, Performance Evaluation, Impact Analysis and Replication Guidelines	ICCS																											D5.4	

Figure 3: WP5 Timeline

5 Planning and Setup of the XGain UCs

The testing and validation plan presented in Chapter 4 has been extensively discussed and agreed upon by all UC leaders and WP5 partners. The UC responsables (UC leaders and UC technical leaders) were asked to use the testing and validation plan in order to define exact testing procedures and activities for their UC and prepare the test site and infrastructure support. In preparation for the start of the testing and validation period (Phase 1 – M16) the UC leaders were requested to provide preparatory material, complying to what is required by the testing and validation plan. This material includes an overview of the UC setup, services addressed and expected outcomes, key roles and interactions within the UC, KPIs for the testing and validation of the technologies, the KFT and the impact assessment, any challenges they expect to face during the execution, risks and assumptions, and an adapted implementation plan and timeline specific to the activities of each UC. This information is presented in Chapters 6 to 11 for all UCs.

5.1 Managing and Monitoring

Operational management within WP5 and the UC execution refers to the systematic planning, coordination, and oversight of day-to-day activities, processes, and resources required to ensure that the UC executions operate effectively and efficiently. A thorough planning and preparation phase has been completed, but more to that continuous monitoring of activities, progress and performance and effective communication and reporting are crucial to remain aligned with the scope of work and achieve the expected outcomes.

The initial and fundamental phase of T5.1 involved establishing the framework for the action plan concerning the organization of the UC environment and determining the next course of action. The adoption of the Deming Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle, outlines the necessary procedures to ensure the effective operation of the tasks and, consequently, the achievement of the WP5 objectives.

5.1.1 Plan-Do-Check-Act

The Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) model is a crucial component of the XGain UC trials execution. This systematic approach serves as a valuable tool to facilitate the ongoing enhancement and refinement of project elements. Also known as the Deming Wheel, the PDCA model is an essential framework that ensures the project's continuous improvement. Within the context of agile management, the PDCA cycle plays a pivotal role, especially when exploring and testing various solutions within a controlled and monitored setting, ultimately leading to the development and improvement of processes and solutions. Figure 4 below describes how the PDCA cycle is applied to the UC trials execution, presenting what activities are undertaken in each step of the cycle.

- Plan and define the **objectives**, establish goals and **expectations** (scope of testing).
- Identify **processes** and **resources** required – planning of testing and validation **strategy** in UCs.
- **Set KPIs (Technology validation, KFT testing, UC impact validation)**
- Specify the way to **record** the plan through the deliverables D5.1, D5.2, D5.3.
- If technologies/impacts do not meet predefined KPIs, **identify** corrective **actions** to make **improvements** – **feeding feedback** to WP3, WP4
→ Refine models, KFT, adjust testing strategy, redefine KPIs.

- **Implementation of the testing and validation strategy.**
- Perform the steps in the **test plan** (Technology testing, KFT testing, UC impact validation).
- **Receive feedback from UC involved & communicate.**
- **Monitor** and **evaluate** the results to ensure they **align** with the objectives and KPIs set in the planning phase.
- **Assess** the **outcomes** of the XGain testing and validation strategy, **compare** to predefined benchmarks and KPIs.
- **Identify** necessary **corrections.**

Figure 4: Deming Plan-Do-Check-Act Cycle

6 XGain UC 1: Rural Community Services (Spain)

6.1 Use Case 1 Overview, Objectives and Expected Outcome

6.1.1 UC1 overview and set-up

El Molló, near Mora la Nova in Catalunya, is characterized by its rural terrain and topology, featuring a set-apart location with large warehouse that contains a 5G lab and plantations around the warehouse that are typical of the region. This area is known for its variety of fruit trees, vegetables, and but also other services like tourism and logistics. Socio-economically, nearby towns like Mora la Nova and Mora d'Ebre, despite their strong community bonds and quality of life, face challenges such as aging populations and the need for better connectivity and services. These towns, emphasize diverse crops and viticulture, reflecting the proximity to the Priorat wine region. The local economy is primarily driven by small and medium-sized enterprises, with less emphasis on large-scale industries, leading to lower average income levels and potential outmigration among the youth.

The pilot area for the XGain project, hosted by i2CAT, requires sophisticated infrastructure to support drone operation and 5G-enabled services. This includes networking, computing, and radio connectivity elements for a private 5G network, as well as public 5G network connectivity. Advanced radio and edge technologies will be used to facilitate various potential drone-related services like precision agriculture and infrastructure inspection. The i2CAT laboratory, already existing in the pilot location, is equipped with computing servers, Wi-Fi, and a fibre/copper-based network infrastructure. The setup, that will be enhanced to include a new private 5G network, is designed as a potential indoor and outdoor training and testing hub for drone-based solutions.

6.1.2 UC1 services

The primary objective of UC1 is the implementation of the drone operations centre. A drone operations centre serves as the foundational platform to introduce different drone-based services to potentially boost and impact on a variety of impact factors (environmental, climate, social) in the community. A drone centre allows users to develop their drone flying skills and to deploy drone-based services in the controlled and supervised lab environment, a base requirement before the actual implementation and execution of drone-based services. As such, it can be stated that one main objective of a drone operations centre is to act as a catalyst in the area, as different UCs and services can emerge from i) knowledge generation and ii) facilitating the testing of drone-based services, as well iii) getting in touch with state-of-the-art technologies like 5G.

In essence, UC1's initiative aims to provide the infrastructure environment in which a drone operations centre could be hosted, not only to support the development and testing of drone services but also playing a pivotal role in advancing knowledge and fostering innovation in the area.

6.1.3 Key Roles and Interactions within UC1

i2CAT leads the UC and has a dedicated team responsible for the pilot planning and execution. The key roles for the pilot execution are (testbed) infrastructure providers, technical support, pilot planning and supervision; all these roles are implemented by the i2CAT team. The testbed is hosted in a space that has been created in collaboration with the county council of Mora d'Ebre. This entity owns the warehouse and essential parts of the (building, energy and networking) infrastructure on top of which the 5G Lab is deployed.

6.1.4 Implementation Plan

The implementation plan can be broken down into a series of activities that each have their own timeline. One base requirement for the implementation of the UC1 pilot is the onboarding of the drone operator to understand the possibilities of the integration and demonstration activities. In parallel, the validation of the 5G network hardware in the i2CAT lab in Barcelona is performed. This activity is followed by the deployment of the 5G network as an addition to the existing base infrastructure. The next activity is the testing and validation of the 5G network by connecting a drone to the 5G network. The final activity is the execution of an actual validation experiment or field trial with a specific scenario that can be implemented with drones (a demonstration of potential rural service). Further, several activities need to be planned in 2025 to involve stakeholders for witnessing the final demonstration, for an on-site workshop(s), for providing their feedback, etc., either in situ or remotely. Figure 5 shows the main milestones of the UC1 pilot. Please note that all milestones are tentative and need to be refined further, as the WP5 progresses.

	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	2024												2025												
	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
UC1				OB			LV			TME	TD			DI				PD							

Figure 5: UC1 implementation plan

The marked milestones are:

- **OB = Onboarding of drone operator.** A drone operator needs to be chosen to enable the deployment of drones and to participate in the integration and demonstration process.
- **LV = Lab Validation.** The 5G network equipment will be tested and validated in the i2CAT lab in Barcelona, before being installed in the pilot site.
- **TME = Technology Mix Evaluation.** As part of WP3 activities, end-to-end tests will be performed that involve mixes of technologies available in the pilot site and/or the i2CAT lab in Barcelona.
- **TD = Testbed Deployment.** The 5G network will be deployed in the pilot site.
- **DI = Drone Integration.** The drone hardware will be integrated via a modem with the 5G network to enable transmission of data from and towards the drone.
- **PD = Pilot Demonstration.** A 5G-enabled demonstration of a drone-based scenario will be executed.

The i2CAT team, composed of technical experts with knowledge about the 5G Lab facilities, contacts for organizing events and with knowledge about the 5G technology to be used, will be responsible for the execution of the different phases of the UC1 pilot.

For the implementation of the 5G-enabled edge infrastructure, the following elements are available:

- Indoor 5G Small Cell
- Outdoor 5G Small Cell
- PowerEdge R6515 servers
- Intel NUCs
- Raspberry Pis
- Network infrastructure (copper/fibre) to interconnect items listed above

- Drone (provided by the subcontracted drone's company)
- An additional edge server (provided by the subcontracted drone's company)

6.2 Mapping of UC1 with KFT functionalities

Given the UC1 pilot is associated to a community level assessment due to its overarching impact on the municipality, it will be of particular interest to evaluate the broader impact factor assessment predictions performed by the KFT on level beyond the simple drone operations centre facility. For this community level evaluation, the KPIs will be a mix of technological, economical, and socio-environmental impact factors that are particularly relevant for a drones' operation centre. This, among others, will include the evaluation of the cost for setting up and maintaining the necessary infrastructure, the revenue growth per year, carbon footprint, numbers of trainings performed for local community, etc.

A user that would be interested in deploying such a drone operations centre, should be able to get a proper assessment by the KFT to determine how the centre could impact in some of those factors. One main output of the KFT should be a proper techno-economic analysis to understand whether the investment can make sense or not. Further, knowledge about the future readiness of the proposed installations will be key to understand if the investment is worthwhile. In drone operations, it can be expected that state of the art technologies needs to be present, so the solutions proposed by the KFT should include these technologies in the proposed technology mixtures. The KFT also should provide an option that considers sharing the infrastructure with other services, such as the more generic high data rate access that can be enabled by 5G. This latter point, i.e., the sharing of the infrastructure across multiple services, should also be considered by the KFT: by indicating potential other services, apart from the drone operations, the KFT should be able to perform an assessment that considers the combination of services in a single infrastructure at least for the techno-economic analysis, but also potentially for other impact factors.

6.3 UC1 Test Scenarios

The drone operating centre's testbed is designed with two fundamental objectives in mind. Firstly, it employs a drone to obtain real-time video recordings for a rural service, which could cover domains like agricultural monitoring, livestock surveillance, and infrastructure inspection, the latter being the one chosen for UC1. Infrastructure evaluation includes the crucial task of identifying wear and tear in wind turbine blades, essential for the upkeep of renewable energy facilities. These highlight the role of drones in elevating the precision and efficiency of operations within rural scenarios.

Beyond the showcase of drone applications, the testbed could also serve an educational role. Subjected to the contracted drone company, training sessions could be offered on the complexities of drone operations to users. Post-training, users could obtain skill in piloting drones within controlled environments. The added facet of the 5G connectivity not only enhances data transmission capabilities but also augments a range of drone services, presenting users with a holistic view of the potential of integrated drone operations. Furthermore, the captured video isn't just stored. Instead, through the integration of 5G technology, the visual feed is transmitted to a dedicated edge infrastructure, ensuring low latency and high throughput. This is where edge processing comes into play. Data could be processed either on the far edge or on the near edge.

However, several parameters need monitoring to ensure the operation's success. Among these are the quality and stability of the transmitted video feed over 5G, the efficiency with which the computing device processes

and renders the images, the ability and knowledge with which newly trained users control the drones, and other KPIs perhaps not so straightforward to see, such as the impact generated by expanding knowledge about 5G and drones. On a technical level, the scenarios also shall be used to execute measurements of radio signal quality to better understand the behaviour of the 5G technology so this information can be fed back to the KFT.

As such, within the overall pilot execution, two specific scenarios are envisioned to be executed in the format of practical demonstrations or so-called test scenarios. These two test scenarios are intended to showcase the capability of a state-of-the-art private 5G infrastructure, and the usage of 5G-enabled drones and they are as follows:

1. Demonstrating a live video feed capture from a drone for a typical rural service, e.g. detection of material degradation in the blades of wind turbines or pest control in plantations, processed and displayed in real-time through 5G infrastructure.
2. Training users to proficiently fly drones in a controlled environment, while optionally benefiting from 5G connectivity for their services. (Subjected to the contracted drone company; if not possible, this could derive into a scenario for just showcasing capacities of a 5G network for a media service)

Table 6 below shows the two test scenarios identified for testing the technology mixtures.

Table 6: UC1 Test Scenarios for Technology Mixtures

XGain UC – Service	UC1 – Rural Community Services		
Scenario 1	Demonstrating a live video feed capture from a drone		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
A drone equipped with a camera and a 5G modem flies over or close to the target area or objective to produce a video that is sent to the infrastructure over 5G and that is processed in the edge.	The video is transmitted without losses and with small delays towards the edge application, where it is processed.	TBC after measurement	The capturing of the video will be done live, it is TBD how the drone operator processes the video, i.e., live or in post-processing.
Scenario 2	Training of users while benefiting from 5G		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes

<p>One or several users are trained to fly a drone. Using the 5G capacities, a service, e.g. live video transmission from the drone, can be enabled.</p>	<p>The users learn basic manoeuvring of a drone, while witnessing the capacities of the 5G network.</p>	<p>TBC after measurement</p>	<p>If drone training cannot be done, depending on the drone operator’s capacity, the scenario can just focus on 5G capacities for media services.</p>
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For the implementation of the 5G-enabled edge infrastructure, the following elements are available:

- Indoor 5G Small Cell
- Outdoor 5G Small Cell
- PowerEdge R6515 servers
- Intel NUCs
- Raspberry Pis
- Network infrastructure (copper/fibre) to interconnect items listed above

The Small Cells are Cablefree³ solutions and they are Amarisoft⁴-based, a 4G/5G-enabling solution that will be used to create 5G NR testbed. It will operate in band n77, which is the 5G-band available for testing purposes. A spectrum request needs to be approved by the Spanish ministry; the entity decides the specific frequency range and bandwidth that will be available for experimentation. From previous experience, up to 40 MHz are assigned close to the 4 GHz frequency. The larger part of the equipment budget was spent on these 5G small cells. Most of the remaining budget is allocated to the computing elements.

For computational processing, UC1 is set to deploy a dual-layer edge computing architecture to handle the generated data. This system is differentiated into what are typically referred to as the far edge and near edge layers. The far edge consists of compact devices situated in proximity to where the data originates, allowing for swift initial processing. Conversely, the near edge is composed of more robust computing machinery, positioned within the warehouse facilities, to manage more complex data processing tasks. An already existing networking infrastructure that includes switches, fibres and ethernet connections will be used to interconnect the radio and computing elements.

The personnel involved in the UC1 will include i2CAT researchers that will perform most of the tasks that are executed as part of operation and maintenance and the experimentations. The activities of the i2CAT teams are fully funded by the XGain project. The drone operation and drone scenario execution are handled by a third party (EbreDrone) that is paid via subcontracting.

³ [CableFree: 4G & 5G 10 Gigabit Wireless Technology](#)

⁴ [Software company dedicated to 4G LTE and 5G NR - Amarisoft](#)

6.3.1 UC1 Data Definition

To measure the technical aspects of the UC1 experimental scenarios, data sets related to the performance of the three infrastructure segments (radio, transport, computation) will be collected. The interaction between the drone, equipped with a 5G modem, and the edge, where the service is running, the video is consumed, etc., will serve as scenario to collect data sets from the end-to-end connection, measures as part of the technical KPI evaluation. The data sets collected will include:

- Network Latency and Throughput
- Resource Utilization
- E2E Response Time
- Processing Response Time
- Service Availability and Reliability

This data will be collected by using the tools iperf, ping, and some python scripts, to measure the raw performance of the UC deployment and they will be stored locally. Given the anonymity of the data sets (no specific user associated), the data will also be shared without any limitations in the corresponding deliverables that report the outcome of the experiments.

Beyond the technical data sets collected from experiments, data sets related to the impact factor assessment, the usage and usability of the KFT, and the experiment execution will be collected based on user feedback. These data sets will include subjective impressions of the pilot about how well the conjunction of technologies and services based on drones worked, as well as survey-style data that will reflect the opinion of the participants (stakeholders and team members) on several KPIs that are relevant for the KPI collection. This information will be anonymous, but we might collect key information relevant for the information gathering done in the project, such as whether a participant is a farmer, an SME, a govern entity, etc. Participants will fill out a form in which they agree on the data they wish to share to avoid any GDPR issues.

Any data produced will be stored in the project's file storage platform and data sets will be added to the DMP of the project.

6.4 UC1 Challenges, Risks and Assumptions

A key challenge for UC1 will be to measure non-technical KPIs, since they go beyond the execution of a demonstration scenario (technical). For gathering social acceptance, for example, stakeholders and participants of the pilot will need to provide their assessment, which will be obtained by surveys, workshops or training sessions. A thorough and continuous planning of these activities will be necessary to obtain the desired outputs.

Further, a challenge is to depend on the third-party drone operator for the technical demonstration and potential training sessions. Given the third party must be contracted with a limited budget, the scope of the activities will be limited as well: execution of drone flights for testing, validation and demonstration purposes, as well as potential drone training classes need to be considered. We assume that just a few days of activities can be executed to showcase the drone technologies. Also, it could be that some potential third-party drone operator companies might not be willing to participate in all project activities and the pilot tasks, such as integration or demonstration. UC1 lead will try to find the drone operators that best adjusts to the

requirements, even if not all can be met. The possible choices will be limited to local drone operators from the pilot area.

A clear risk for UC1 lies in obtaining the spectrum for the 5G network operation from the Spanish ministry. There is no guarantee that the spectrum will be granted and how much bandwidth will be assigned in case we obtain permission. The risk is potentially higher for the outdoor coverage than for the indoor coverage. In case the spectrum should not be granted, alternative ways of showcasing the drone operation will be considered, e.g. using a Wi-Fi6 connectivity, instead of 5G.

6.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Overview of XGain UC1

6.5.1 Technology mixture testing KPIs

The targeted pilot setup involves a mix of radio access, transport and edge computing technologies: a 5G NR SA network will be used to enable a data channel between the drone, equipped with a 5G modem, and the 5G small cells. The small cells include the technology to transform the radio transmissions into data packets that can be sent over the infrastructure's wired network fabric, and vice-versa. Over ethernet or fibre (to be determined), the data will be then forwarded to an edge node, where the computational tasks take place, i.e., the processing of the video streamed from the drone.

While in WP3 an isolated analysis of the three segments is performed, in the pilot the end-to-end connection including the ICT technologies is considered, along with the service that consumes the data sent by the drones. The evaluations include the following KPIs in Table 7 (note that this list might be modified include or exclude elements to best adapt to the technology mix evaluations necessary to validate the KFT):

Table 7: UC1 Technology Mixture Testing KPIs

KPI	Target value	Calculation method
Network Latency	Duration: 3 minutes Number of executions: 3	Measure the end-to-end round-trip time of data exchanged between the origin device (drone) and the service executed in the edge.
Network throughput	Duration: 3 minutes Number of executions: 3	Measure data rate (in Mbps) per end device (downlink/uplink).
Jitter	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3	Measure the variation in the latency of received packets.
Computing Resource Utilization	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3	Monitor CPU and RAM usage of the processing devices.
E2E Response Time	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3	Measure how long it takes from the creation of data or request in a drone and the reception of the drone and processed in the edge.

Processing Response Time	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3	Measure time between data reception in the service, e.g. video data, and a service response generated at the processing node
Service Availability	Duration: 10 minutes Number of executions: 5	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users (%)
Service Reliability	Duration: 3 minutes Number of executions: 5	Ratio of time the service performs the expected functions, e.g., object detection (%)

The testing of these KPIs will be done in different contexts:

1. Tests performed as part of the initial technology and testbed validations. These will exclude the drone service.
2. The tests performed on-ground, i.e., with the drone, but without the drone being airborne. These tests can include the drone service running in the compute node.
3. The tests performed with airborne drones, that feature all segments and the drone service.

6.5.2 Impact assessment KPIs

It is important to highlight that a drone centre per se does not implement any agricultural services, such as precision agriculture, forest management, or land use, where drones are deployed to improve the capacities and efficiency of farmers. Instead, the drone centre acts as booster for such services, implementing a place where farmers can train the use of drones and where they can gather first experiences of deploying services. As such, to measure the impact of the drone operations centre at a community level, there are two ways to measure it:

- Direct impact: the drone operations centre per se, as a place where demo services are implemented, employees are working, facilities are offered, etc., has a direct effect on a variety of impact factors. This includes the generation of workplaces, spreading awareness and knowledge of digital technologies that can be used by farmers, drawing attraction of farmers, SMEs and others to the drone centre site where experiences and knowledge can be exchange among them, etc.
- Indirect impact: a drone operations centre is expected to work as a catalyst for deploying new technologies and services that are based on drones in a community or region. As such, an estimation can be made on the potential impact such a drone centre can have in a variety of impact factors.

At this stage of the project, the KPIs shown in Table 8 are targeted to be identified (the final KPIs to be evaluated might differ).

Table 8: UC1 impact assessment KPIs

Impact	KPI	Calculation method	Validation method
Economic	Expected job creation in the area	Estimate expected increase in jobs that are related to drone operations (operation, maintenance, analysis).	Interview drone operators on company size and map to XGain drone centre.

Economic	Expected increase in yield from drone services	Estimate expected savings and revenues from new service opportunities that can be implemented by drone services in the rural sectors, which become available from training and testing in the centre.	Study scenario without drones and compare to when drones would be used.
Economic/Social	Attraction potential for education and innovation	Estimate amount of attraction (in persons) that converge in the drone operations centre to benefit from the added value beyond learning drone operations training.	Explore currently engaged associations and users that are using the 5G lab and extrapolate to the future.
Environmental (indirect)	Reduction in electricity consumption and CO2 emissions	Estimate the average cost in electricity and the average CO2 emission before implementing drone-based methodologies in one service (e.g. precision farming techniques).	Estimate cost/consumption information for a specific service and replace some activities with drones. Calculate new cost/consumption.
Environmental (indirect)	Resource Optimization	Assess the resource efficiency by tracking inputs such as the quantity of water, fertilizers, and pesticides used per hectare of land before and after the implementation of an example service that can be implemented by drones (e.g. precision farming techniques).	Estimate consumption information for a specific service and replace some activities with drones. Calculate new consumption.
Environmental (indirect)	Environmental Impact	Assess the reduction in environmental impact, such as reduced chemical usage or carbon emissions. Quantify the reduction in waste by comparing the amount of unused or excess resources (e.g., unused pesticides) before and after adopting a drone-based service, e.g. precision farming.	Estimate impact for a specific service and replace some activities with drones. Calculate new consumption.
Social	Skills Development	Evaluate the impact of the project on the development of local drone operation skills.	Estimate number of people that can be trained per year.
Social	Community Engagement	Measure the engagement of local communities and educational institutions in in drone and/or 5G technologies.	Assess local associations/SMEs/institutions that can be related to the drone centre (dissemination/pilot/workshop/evaluation participants).

Social	Digital literacy	Improvement in the community's digital skills and literacy due to new technology exposure.	On-site training about drone-related services.
Social	Public Perception of Drones	Community's acceptance and perception of drones and their impact.	Survey

7 XGain UC 2: e-Health (Greece)

7.1 Use Case 2 Overview, Objectives and Expected Outcome

7.1.1 UC2 overview and set-up

The pilot test of the Greek Use Case will be implemented in one of the many remote areas of the Region of Central Macedonia. Central Macedonia is a diverse region with high mountains surrounding extensive plains and several rivers. The area where the pilot test will be conducted has not yet been specified as many parameters are still being considered in terms of reaching end users. The ideal scenario is for the CAPTAIN Box device to be installed in the homes of elderly people who live mostly alone without much of a social life and wish to attend various educational seminars of various skills they would like to learn as well as cultural events. The socio-economic impact from this action will increase the quality of life of the person in the field of education and will also give an incentive to the policy makers to design new strategies towards the elderly for various actions that may be related to them.

In the current UC pilot there will be no installation of external 5G infrastructure, but since the CAPTAIN Box device to be installed in the homes of older adults' needs to be connected to the Internet, it will need to use existing infrastructure from the homes of the older adults if they have access to the internet via Wi-Fi, otherwise it will need to use an external adapter installed on the device. In this case we can measure and evaluate the existing connectivity infrastructure in place to compare how the use of 5G in the remote areas could benefit. A similar test will be conducted in the Living Lab of ICCS with the use of 5G and based on those measurements we will be able to extract results for its effectiveness and efficiency.

7.1.2 UC2 services

The primary objective is to enhance and empower the socialization of lonely people who will use and interact with the device and highlight the problem of insufficient broadband in remote and rural areas. In several remote areas of Greece, and especially due to the current UC, in Central Macedonia, the elderly feel alienated and due to a lack of interest either from their relatives or from the state, while many of them would like to feel that they are contributing and offering in society they don't have the way and the means to do it. This creates many problems for them, either they cannot communicate with their loved ones or visit a doctor and more to exercise their mind and be more independent and active. It will also educate and coach older adults through various interventions from the CAPTAIN Box that focus beyond the social part in the areas of physical exercise, dietary fiber intake, and mental enhancement. In this way, elderly people become even more independent, and their quality of life is increased.

The expected result will be for the elderly to be able to interact with the device even if they are not digital literate, to attend cultural events and to be able to train with various crafts. Beyond this, will also be able to verify the state of networking in remote areas and raise awareness among government agencies to highlight the problem and importance of such technological infrastructures.

7.1.3 Key Roles and Interactions within UC2

The key partners contributing and interacting in UC2 are: **CAPTAIN** (UC leader) responsible for setting up the CAPTAIN Box devices for home installation, developing the additional components for 5G connectivity and provide technical support for the system installation, and providing support to RDFCM for technical issues

arising during the pilot; **RDFCM** responsible for the identification of stakeholders and participants recruitment based on the identified inclusion/exclusion criteria, handling the ethics application., and day-to-day communications with participants for feedback collection; and **ICCS** (UC technical leader) responsible for conducting a simulation with CAPTAIN Box device on the lab environment with 5G connectivity.

7.1.4 Implementation Plan

Some new features should be implemented to support the scenario. Next, we need to identify in which elderly people’s homes we should install the device and consider the infrastructure of the area. For those homes that do not have an existing Internet infrastructure, an adapter will be added to the device, and we will analyse and compare the responses of one connectivity solution (Wi-Fi) to the other (4G or 5G adapter). Also, those results will be validated with the results of a Living Lab that conduct research with 5G connectivity.

The CAPTAIN's team in collaboration with the RDFCM team will contact the local authorities in some of the remote areas of Central Macedonia, initially to identify the people who are going to use the device, the analysis and planning will be done on how and of the device will be installed and then daily we will contact the users to get feedback on how much the device has helped them.

The UC2 implementation plan timeline is shown in Figure 6, with some UC-specific milestones.

2023			2024												2025							
12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36		
Milestone 1			Milestone 2			Milestone 3			Milestone 4			Milestone 5			Milestone 6			Milestone 7				

Figure 6: UC2 Implementation Plan

Milestone 1: Development of new CAPTAIN Box features.

Milestone 2: Testing new features.

Milestone 3: LL Test with 5G or 4G adapters.

Milestone 4: LL Test from ICCS.

Milestone 5: LLs Validation.

Milestone 6: Find rural area and end users to deploy CAPTAIN Box.

Milestone 7: Deploy CAPTAIN Box devices.

7.2 Mapping of UC2 with KFT functionalities

The differentiation with other UCs lies in the fact that the KFT will not be used by end users but by caregivers, stakeholders, government agencies and more generally health-related agencies. The morphology of the area where a facility is to be built should be considered so that the respective governmental and non-governmental body invests in it to see if it is worth the effort and investment. Of course, it should be analysed whether the installation of a network infrastructure could benefit other activities running in the area.

7.3 UC2 Test Scenarios

Within the context of the UC to be executed, the most basic scenario is to exploit and analyse the performance of connectivity, because end users are needed to watch a live or on-demand cultural event (theatrical or musical) with high-definition video and audio. Moreover, another scenario is to educate users via online

courses to learn some crafts or enhance some other skills depending on their choice. In these cases, we could compare results based on the existing network of the user's device.

In case the user does not have network infrastructure, a 4G or 5G adapter is needed to be implemented in CAPTAIN Box.

The personnel involved in the UC will include CAPTAIN’s researchers and RDFCM colleagues that will perform any technical or non-technical support.

The technology testing test scenarios that have been identified are shown below in Table 9.

Table 9: UC2 Test Scenarios for Technology Mixtures

XGain UC - Service	UC2: Rural Services, eHealth (GR)		
Scenario 1	Connect CAPTAIN Box to network adapter and monitor network traffic		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
The test involves installing a network adapter with the CAPTAIN Box device and monitoring measurements.	Successfully connection to Internet and syncing data with CAPTAIN’s server.	TBC after measurement	
Scenario 2	Video streaming using CAPTAIN Box device		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
We will try to broadcast with very high resolution video and audio, a half-hour long video and take measurements from this interaction.	We expect the retransmission to be without delays.	TBC after measurement	
Scenario 3	Monitor CAPTAIN Box device in Living with 5G connectivity		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes

<p>The main idea is to represent in a Living Lab with 5G connectivity, CAPTAIN Box device to interact with end users.</p>	<p>We expect that the CAPTAIN Box device is going to connect to 5G.</p>	<p>TBC after measurement</p>	<p>Any other relevant information e.g., Near real time data from the field also reduces the amount of irrigation water.</p>
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7.3.1 UC2 Data Definition

CAPTAIN Box device collects data from various sensors and analyses it locally. The only data that is sent out is about the person's overall behaviour for each day which is completely anonymous for GDPR compliance. A RGB camera detects the skeleton and then the face of a person, and proceeds with the authentication of the person to start the analysis. The analysis records user behaviour, such as how long they sit or how long they move, and how fast they move around the space as well as where in the room they stand most of the time. This data is used to enable the system to suggest interventions to improve their mobility. It also captures the user's emotions each time they have a sharp image, as well as analysing their mood before an intervention begins as well as when it is completed. These results are also compared with the audio mood analysis every time the system expects a command from the user. In addition, after each intervention the users are asked if they liked it so that the system knows whether to show them something similar in the following days. Each evening, the day's schedule is adjusted based on this feedback. All this data is collected in a single file which is fully anonymous and is used for model analysis, and sent to the CAPTAIN server for further analysis. This analysis does not adjust anything to the user's program since, as mentioned, this is done locally for each device, but this analysis gives metrics to determine the quality of life of the person while using the device. These measurements are compared with questionnaires conducted before the device is installed. Each audio and video file are only temporarily stored locally on each device, and after the analysis is completed the corresponding files are deleted. No other file that constitutes personal data of the user is sent through the internet.

7.4 UC2 Challenges, Risks and Assumptions

- Challenges:
 - Approach stakeholders to get the profile of older adults that already are in touch.
 - Convince them to install the device and show them the benefits of this experience.
 - The fact that there is a camera on the device may raise some issues.
 - To give them the incentive not to be afraid to interact with the device.
 - For every intervention, the system asks if the user wants to join. It is unclear if the user doesn't want to join so we don't get any feedback.
- Risks:
 - Because the device is small, there is always the possibility that the user will accidentally drop it from the point where it will be placed, resulting in breaking the projector or another component. In that case of computer replacement, the user's current progress cannot be transferred to another device.

7.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Overview of XGain UC2

7.5.1 Technology mixture testing KPIs

The KPIs that have been identified so far for the testing of the technology mixtures in UC2 are shown in Table 10 (note that this list might be modified to best adapt to the technology mixture evaluation to validate the KFT):

Table 10: UC2 Technology Mixture Testing KPIs

KPI
Network throughput
Network latency
Jitter
Resource utilization
Processing latency
Processing response time
Resource utilization
Service Reliability

7.5.2 Impact assessment KPIs

Considering that we do not have a clear picture of which remote areas of Central Macedonia where the scenario will be executed, have the infrastructure to connect to the Internet, there will be an indirect impact on the governmental agencies to upgrade the existing network and the necessity of this infrastructure for other uses that may create new technological infrastructures.

An important impact for the end users will be the enhancement of their sociability and psychology, in which case it will be measured through questionnaires how their life was before in terms of independent living, their psychology and their social life and how it affected them afterwards with the use of the device. Based on these results, the various policymakers and stakeholders can formulate strategies for the elderly.

A tentative selection of KPIs to assess has been made in Table 11. The final KPIs to measure will be better defined after the start of UC execution.

Table 11: UC2 impact assessment KPIs

Impact	KPI	Calculation Method	Validation method
Social	Improve Socialization	Conducting questionnaires about their social life and their association with other people before and after CAPTAIN Box installation.	
Social	Digital Literacy	Conducting questionnaires before and after CAPTAIN Box installation for the current digital skills.	
Social	Skills and Education Development	Through CAPTAIN Box, showing available educational courses.	Conducting quizzes from CAPTAIN Box

			that ask user some questions.
Technological	Network Coverage	Existing network infrastructure.	How much coverage has improved.
Environmental	Electricity Power Consumption	Smart plugs	-
Economic	System cost	TBC	TBC

8 XGain UC 3: Remote Community (UK)

8.1 Use Case 3 Overview, Objectives and Expected Outcome

8.1.1 UC3 overview and set-up

The Isles of Scilly are a small group of Islands remotely situated in the Atlantic Ocean, 30 miles from mainland UK (Figure 7). With five inhabited islands (St Mary's, Tresco, St Martin's, Bryher and St Agnes), there is a combined population of around 2,100 residents. This increases from April to October with 100,000 visitors per year.

Figure 7: The Isles of Scilly in relation to the UK (in bottom left corner of the map)

Geographically, the Islands are a series of low hills, with some tree cover. The hilly nature of the place, combined with just one mobile transmitting station, means that mobile coverage is somewhat patchy - ranging from very good to non-existent. Scilly has a national landscape designation as an Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONB), signifying the importance and beauty of the landscape and seascape. One of the implications of this is that planning is more stringent, and development is restricted in order to protect the special character of the landscape.

Socio-economically, the Islands are significantly poorer than many places across the UK. The average income per capita is around £18,500 (2020) compared with a national average of £30,500 (2020). This is largely due to the seasonal nature of jobs, and a lack of highly skilled and therefore well-paid employment. Tourism accounts for around 85% of the local economy.

In the Isles of Scilly, 5G coverage is available but has "dead points," necessitating reliable data connectivity for soil, water, and meteorological sensors. This connectivity is crucial for informed decision-making, such as irrigation planning. To deploy the CAFA multirobot system effectively, specific infrastructure preparations are required. The system, featuring a 5G drone, can extend network coverage to address dead points, but compliance with local regulations and environmental guidelines is essential. The ground team needs training in setting up and operating the Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV), placing soil moisture sensors, and managing the tethered drone. Engaging with local communities is vital to ensure technology alignment with their socio-economic needs.

8.1.2 UC3 services

UC3 revolves around the development of a technological solution aimed at enhancing agricultural practices. The primary functions of this system include measuring soil humidity, detecting plant diseases, identifying early signs of drought, and transmitting data about these changes to a cloud server in real-time. The implementation of such a system has significant benefits for farming. It reduces the reliance on heavy machinery, leading to less field damage and lower operational costs. Additionally, by providing precise information on crop and soil conditions, it helps in protecting crops, maintaining soil fertility, and optimizing water usage. This ensures that irrigation is more efficient, thus conserving water resources. Overall, the technology promises to make farming more sustainable and environmentally friendly.

8.1.3 Key Roles and Interactions within UC3

CAFA Tech leads the UC and has a dedicated team responsible for the pilot planning and execution. Project partner JS will act as a test case by using their farm Scilly Organics, a 5 acre (2 hectare) organic market garden, as an example of a farm that could be better digitally connected.

8.1.4 Implementation Plan

The implementation time plan for testing & validation for UC3 is given below in Figure 8.

	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35
Development work and tests in Estonia																				
Tests in UK																				
Development work and additoinal tests in Estonia																				
Tests in UK																				
Minor updates and tests in Estonia																				
Final tests in UK																				

Figure 8: UC3 Implementation Plan

8.2 Mapping of UC3 with KFT functionalities

In the Isles of Scilly, the KFT will be vital in evaluating the impact of introducing a multirobot system. The KFT will focusing on how this system affects the local community, economy, and environment. It will provide a techno-economic analysis to see if the investment makes sense, considering both costs and potential benefits like better farming and new job skills for residents. The KFT will also check how the multirobot fits with the Isles' strict environmental rules and explore if its 5G network can be used for other community services.

8.3 UC3 Test Scenarios

Test scenarios for the testing of technology mixtures in the field have been identified and presented below in Table 12.

Table 12: UC3 Test Scenarios for Technology Mixtures

XGain UC - Service	UC3: Remote Community (UK)		
Scenario 1	Taking soil humidity measurements with a robot		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes

<p>The robot drives to the field and insert sensors 20-25 cm deep into the soil. The mobile robot will measure the ground, recording GPS coordinates, timestamps, and measurement IDs at the same time.</p>	<p>The data on soil humidity will be collected and recorded accurately</p>	<p>TBC after measurement</p>	<p>Near real time data from the field also reduces the amount of irrigation water</p>
<p>Scenario 2</p>	<p>Computer vision and processing</p>		
<p>Scenario Test Procedure</p>	<p>Expected Results</p>	<p>Actual Results</p>	<p>Additional Notes</p>
<p>Drone with on-board camera is tethered to the mobile robot, which provides energy to the drone over the tether cable. Drone takes aerial images of the field, which are sent over the tether cable to the mobile robot's GPU unit for near real time processing.</p>	<p>The tethered drone captures aerial field images and transmits them via its tether cable to the mobile robot's GPU for near real-time processing. The image processing is fast and accurate, reflecting current field conditions.</p>	<p>TBC after measurement</p>	<p>Aerial survey eliminates the frequent need for heavy machinery on fields (so we can avoid unnecessary damages for the soil).</p>
<p>Scenario 3</p>	<p>Expanding wireless network</p>		
<p>Scenario Test Procedure</p>	<p>Expected Results</p>	<p>Actual Results</p>	<p>Additional Notes</p>
<p>Expanding wireless network from the drone via a 5G router.</p>	<p>The 5G WiFi router ensures data coverage within a 700-meter radius.</p>	<p>TBC after measurement</p>	

8.3.1 UC3 Data Definition

In this UC, soil humidity data is gathered using sensors that transmit measurements to a cloud server. Farmers access this information on soil humidity through their Agri GIS server, enabling informed watering decisions. The CAFA Multirobot System integrates a sophisticated UGV with an aerial drone deployable from the robot. The tethered drone serves both as a power source and a data connection, transmitting 5G signals to the UGV's computer system. Equipped with a 5G WiFi Router and RGB/NIR cameras, the drone ensures data coverage within a 700-meter radius. The CAFA VideoLyzer software on a connected computer analyzes the camera feed,

identifying plant health, detecting early signs of drought, spotting pests, and recognizing emerging diseases. Timestamped NIR images are valuable for monitoring pest damage progression on crops.

8.4 UC3 Challenges, Risks and Assumptions

The biggest challenge lies in developing a multirobot system that meets the needs of farmers, as we have not yet received final feedback from them. Farmers have been occupied with fieldwork during the spring, summer, and autumn periods.

Our first visit to the Scilly Islands is planned for May 2024. During this visit, we will be able to gather more detailed information on the farmers' requirements. Additionally, we anticipate obtaining comprehensive feedback on weather and soil conditions.

8.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Overview of XGain UC3

8.5.1 Technology mixture testing KPIs

The technological KPIs defined in the planning stage for the testing of technology mixtures in the field for UC3 are shown below in Table 13. This is a tentative selection and will be better defined after the initiation of the testing period.

Table 13: UC3 Technology Mixture Testing KPIs

KPI	Target value	Calculation method
Resource Utilization	Duration: 30 minutes Number of executions: 3	Analyse the resource utilization of each layer. Monitor CPU and RAM usage of the devices running the same app under different scenario.
Network throughput	Duration: 30 seconds Number of executions: 10	Data rate (in Mbps) required per end device (downlink/uplink).
Power-consumption	Duration: 30 minutes Number of executions: 3	Power consumption monitoring. Energy efficiency optimization.
Service Availability	Duration: 10 minutes Number of executions: 5	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users (%).
Bandwidth Test	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 1 per device	Obtain measurements of the bandwidth available between devices. If Internet connectivity is available, a seedtest.net experiment could be beneficial to perform.
Network Latency Test	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 1 per device	Measure network latency by pinging different points of the infrastructure.

8.5.2 Impact assessment KPIs

A tentative selection of KPIs to evaluate impact assessment has been made, shown in in Table 14. The final KPIs to measure will be better defined after the start of UC execution.

Table 14: UC3 impact assessment KPIs

Impact	KPI	Baseline values	Calculation method	Validation method
Technological	Soil humidity measurement	2 measurements per week	How many measurements per week	Number of measurements increases
Technological	Network Coverage area	Current network coverage area	Mapping the area covered by the 5G WiFi router from the drone.	How much coverage has improved
Environmental	Use of fertilizers	Current amount of fertilizer use	Monitor the total amount of fertilizers that have been used in a specific area during the growing season.	Soil health assessment
Environmental	Amount of irrigation water	Current amount of irrigation water	Monitor the total amount of irrigation water that has been used in a specific area during the growing season.	The amount of irrigation water has reduced
Social	Improved connectivity and communication for tourists	Current connectivity and communication for tourists	Mapping the area where tourists have connectivity,	Connectivity and communication for tourists have improved
Economic	Yield of crops	Current yield of crops	Yield of crops in kg/year.	Yield of crops have increased
Economic	Human resource	Current number of employees	The number of employees after the introduction of the multirobot.	Reduction in the number of employees

9 XGain UC 4: Farming and Forestry (Lithuania)

9.1 Use Case 4 Overview, Objectives and Expected Outcome

9.1.1 UC4 overview and set-up

Forest monitoring and evaluation of certain properties (e.g., fire risk, pest infestation, drought affected areas, etc.) is envisioned as the service provided by the UC. The developed service is based on a multicopter drone equipped with high-end hyperspectral camera. Hyperspectral cameras provide valuable information, but collect a vast amount of data therefore a lot of processing power is required to extract and infer the results from the raw data. In certain cases, timing is much of importance since immediate action can be taken to eliminate the hazards and prevent losses and damages. While there are multiple scenarios for the application of the service in practice, the UC focuses on monitoring and investigation of fire risks in forests. The UC4 deployment is planned in Lithuania over the forest covered terrain, that would be bigger than 50ha. The service provided by UC4 is focusing on bringing benefits to the population dwelling next to the forests (fire hazard prevention services), forest rangers (application of the technology might reduce the forest research costs and human power; will increase the digitalization of the forestry, and might create new workplaces for drone operators, or upgrade the skills of the workers employed now).

The data collected by the input device (camera – Specim AFX10) is transmitted to data server (NAS) using Edge computing device (NVIDIA Jetson) and 5G router (Teltonika RUTX50) in real time attached to a drone. The infrastructure of mounting a micro pc, camera and a 5G router should not change in the field-testing environment. The connection to the mobile network tower can be lower if the distance between the drone and the tower is longer. Data storage infrastructure is static, and there are no changes between Lab testing and the possible field testing or the location of the field testing.

Figure 9: UC4 technologies and user equipment

9.1.2 UC4 services

The UC4 piloting activities focus on bringing a technological solution that could be used for various forest management services:

- Forest health data collection

- Forest fire prevention
- Biodiversity monitoring
- (Il)legal forest logging identification
- Wild animal monitoring
- Other services (lost person detection, illegal construction, etc)

The technological solution of data transmission could be easily transferred to precision agriculture as well.

9.1.3 Key Roles and Interactions within UC4

The key roles and responsibilities within UC4 are: **ART21** (UC leader) responsible for planning and executing field trials, managing activities, and implementation of technologies, collecting data, engaging with stakeholders, and reporting progress; and **eBOS** (UC technical leader) to provide technical support to UC leader on technical issues.

9.1.4 Implementation Plan

The UC project implementation timeline is provided below in Figure 10.

Figure 10: UC4 Implementation Plan

We might need two UAV pilots. Device list is static and includes:

- DJI Matrice 600 – drone;
- Specim AFX10 – camera;
- Teltonika RUTX50 – 5G router
- NVIDIA Jetson – micro PC;
- NAS server – data storage;

9.2 Mapping of UC4 with KFT functionalities

The KFT functionalities that would allow a better user guidance to choose the service would include:

The KFT user would be able to set as many query parameters as possible to make sure that his/her needs are met (i.e. connectivity solutions already in place – FR.06, terrain details, weather conditions – FR12). Moreover, to set the minimum and maximum budget for the possible solution – FR13. To manage socio-economic factors, the user might input the budget cost query and base the technological mix depending on the possible saving amount.

To involve the community into the UC deployment the results should be visualized at the same instance, meaning that some kind of dashboard is required, where the data collection, analysis and results would be displayed. To make the dashboard more interactive it would be good to have a possibility to ask questions, the KFT provider or the UC managers, to get answers about the arising questions regarding the UC analytics and results. The analytical dashboard might have a filtering option, meaning that more communities could use the same instrument, just filter down the results to the respective geographical or social impact area.

9.3 UC4 Test Scenarios

An example of test scenario for UC4 is shown below in Table 15.

Table 15: UC4 Test Scenarios for Technology Mixtures

Scenario 1	Before the warm season approaches local authorities are interested into forest fire prevention and would like to scan 25ha forest to identify fire fuel categories in the territory and get the data over 5 hour time period, with possibility to extend the measurement over a 200ha forest area.		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
Drone, 5G router, Edge device, Hyperspectral camera (angle 90-120 degree), Height – up to 120m Drone speed from 5m/s Coverage area up to 50ha NAS	Drone flight takes up to 25 min. Data transfer up to 5GB while in the air. Area coverage – full (25ha) A successful data transfer between the camera and the NAS	TBD	For 200ha territory, few drone flights will have to be carried out.

9.3.1 UC4 Data Definition

By using the camera – Specim AFX10 we are collecting the Hyperspectral data (ext. “.raw”) depending on the camera settings it can divide the final data into data chunks. The data will be obtained by flying the UAV over the forest area and using the 5G router forwarded to the data storage server. Data storage and management procedures are automated so that the data is downloaded from the camera to the data centre automatically. Later the automatic pipeline picks the data for transformation purposes and ML training and prediction. Data collected is difficult to understand the content for an individual. Specific software is needed to transform it to

get more readable content. This makes the data more private and secure so that not any individual can check the content on the collected data.

9.4 UC4 Challenges, Risks and Assumptions

- Challenges:
 - Lab testing show that 2 mobile operators have only 4G network, but at the project framework we are committed to test 5G – this challenge should be eliminated in the field testing.
 - Custom design modification needed to fit the router and the micro pc to fit under the drone while the camera gimble is already attached.
 - Different power consumption by different instances (micro pc – 5V, camera – 10-30 VDC, router – 9-50VDC, Drone – Dji Matrice 600 power output 26.3VDC).
 - Rainy weather conditions are a challenge to collect the data physically (the equipment is not designed to withstand water); foggy, cloudy weather conditions are a challenge to data quality.
- Risks:
 - Different 5G network strength in the flight area
 - Drone battery shortage
 - File transfer corruption

9.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Overview of XGain UC4

9.5.1 Technology mixture testing KPIs

The technological KPIs defined in the planning stage for the testing of technology mixtures in the field for UC4 are shown below in Table 16. This is a tentative selection and will be better defined after the initiation of the testing period.

Table 16: UC4 Technology Mixture Testing KPIs

KPI	Target value	Calculation method	Validation method
File transfer uninterrupted	99,00%	Check/ensure the transfer resilience to network loss, change of network parameters.	Compare the local data to the received data on the remote server.
Data collection from air	From 25 min	Battery capacity check while the whole IT infrastructure works depending on the battery life.	Drone flight mission plan application is tracking the flight time. Log file can be exported.
Covering area	25-50 ha	Plan the drone mission to cover max area with the time frame given.	The drone flight missions will be planned to the maximum battery capacity, and evaluate if the drone covered the determined mission.
Network capacity	Up to 80 Mbps upload and 250 Mbps Download	Measure the throughput that can be obtained with 5G network.	Log the network speed test to a file while the data transfer is initiated while the whole infrastructure is moving.

9.5.2 Impact assessment KPIs

A tentative selection of KPIs to evaluate impact assessment in UC4 has been made, shown in Table 17. The final KPIs to measure will be better defined after the start of UC execution.

Table 17: UC4 impact assessment KPIs

Impact	KPI
Social	Hours of work per employee, per week
Social	Reduced property loss due to forest fires
Economic	Reduced wood loss due to forest fires
Environmental	Energy use Direct CO ₂ emissions
Environmental	Reduced biodiversity loss due to forest fires
Technological	Measure the efficiency of data transmission from remote areas with limited connectivity

10 XGain UC 5: Aquaculture (Croatia)

10.1 Use Case 5 Overview, Objectives and Expected Outcome

10.1.1 UC5 overview and set-up

The oyster and mussel farm for which a remote water quality monitoring system has been developed in the UC5 is situated on the outskirts of the Šibenik town, Croatia, approximately 4 kilometers from the city center. This farm is strategically located in the Krka River estuary, benefiting from a saltwater environment and a constant supply of nutrients carried by the river. However, the topography of the area is challenging with a steep elevation increase of about 50 meters from the water surface to the bank's top what limits land access. Šibenik, the tenth-largest city in Croatia, serves as the administrative and economic center of the Šibenik-Knin County, with a population of approximately 42,600 people. Its economy is driven by trade, tourism, construction, and metal processing, with an average monthly income of around 1600 EUR. Demographically, the county has a diverse age distribution, with a notable proportion in the 60-69 years age group.

The area where the UC5 will be implemented is protected under the Natura2000 program. This prevents the disturbance of the environment involving construction of roads or infrastructure along the riverbanks. These constraints and topological challenges determine the technical requirements for the developed system. Taking everything into account the system was developed in such a way that when implemented it would be able to work autonomously. The developed technology is comprised of water sensors, LoRaWAN and satellite connectivity enablers, and an edge device. The water sensors will be deployed on a mobile raft which was customised to house the sensors and additional equipment. The usage of a raft enables changing the location of where the water quality monitoring would take place (see Figure 2). All devices used in the developed system will be powered using solar cells.

Figure 11: The picture of a raft used for implementing the water analysis system.

10.1.2 UC5 services

The main objective of the UC5 is the development of an extended network infrastructure for water quality assessment. The UC will demonstrate how an extended network infrastructure developed using LoRaWAN and satellite communication can transmit data from offshore sensors to the central monitoring system where an edge device aggregates data and creates a data package which is then transmitted via the satellite network to a database. The end user can view the data via the designed dashboard platform.

The service is a periodic data transmission of the water quality parameters in the environment and can be used for aquaculture farming or remote water quality assessment. Using the information provided aquaculture farmers or other end users will be able to remotely monitor the water quality parameters and plan their activities accordingly. The reduced amount of physical inspection of water quality will reduce resource use and will help to save and allocate human resources to other farming activities.

The primary stakeholders of the solution are the farmers of various aquaculture species but other stakeholders like members of research and academic institutions, NGOs can benefit by the technology.

10.1.3 Key Roles and Interactions within UC5

The UC involves three different types of partners and stakeholders – farmer, solution provider, partner.

The farmer provides the UC site and the required infrastructure for the implementation of the technology. The farmers also provide the know-how on the basic aquaculture activities and crucial aspects of water quality.

Use case **leader** – **BENCO**, develops the remote water monitoring system by gathering the required components and carrying out the required programming and technical assembly tasks to create a final solution.

The use case **technical partner** - **Astrocast** helps in development activities, provides the necessary satellite network infrastructure and services, and provides relative information regarding the developed solution.

The testing and validation of the system is carried out by the UC solution provided in collaboration with the farmer.

10.1.4 Implementation Plan

The general plan for system testing and validation is presented in Figure 12. The planned activities include the implementation of the system on-site and preparations for testing and validation. These activities will be carried out in order to ensure smooth testing and validation procedures. In case of system errors or bugs, additional efforts in system development (programming, infrastructure, etc.) will be taken.

Moving further, the system testing, and validation will take place. The testing process will be carried out to ensure that each component and the whole system is operational and ready for validation.

Validation will be divided into two rounds to estimate and evaluate average values of the system performance.

Figure 12: UC5 Implementation Plan

The implementation of the system above the already mentioned infrastructure will not require a lot of resources. Human resources will be needed on site to install the system – place, connect and secure each device. No programming or similar tasks are envisioned.

If all processes run smoothly (no hardware or software errors will occur) the system validation will not include human resources. The system should be working and collecting data autonomously, transferring it to the database and visualizing it in the dashboard. Data for evaluation of main system characteristics will also be collected automatically via built in programs.

10.2 Mapping of UC5 with KFT functionalities

The services provided by the UC5 can be mapped with various KFT functionalities since the service location and the end-user requirements provide different factors that must be considered. The KFT functionalities that are planned to be tested during the validation of the solution developed in the UC5 are such:

- When proposing a solution, KFT is supposed to take into account environmental information requirements and topological limitations. It will be estimated whether the KFT proposes a solution meeting the Natura 2000 limitations and remote estimation requirements, similar to the solution developed within the UC.
- KFT should estimate the cost of the solution and requirements for the day-to-day operations. Comparison of the KFT prognosis and real-life estimation will be compared.
- The KFT should be friendly to the users who do not have the specific technological know-how for example fish farm staff. KFT will be shown to the possible end users to test this functionality. Multiple functionalities are relevant in such testing: saving and loading sessions, availability of explanation pop-ups, possibility to choose the technological proficiency level, availability of the KFT on various devices.

10.3 UC5 Test Scenarios

The basic test scenario of the developed water quality evaluation system is straightforward. The water sensors connected to the LoRaWAN transmitter via a cable will be deployed in an oyster farm some distance from the shore. The data from the sensors via a LoRaWAN network will be transmitted to the LoRaWAN gateway located on the shore. The edge device connected to the LoRaWAN gateway collects, aggregates and stores the data. This data is then transferred to the database using a satellite network. The device enabling the satellite network is also connected to the edge unit. Data stored in the database is read using an API and visualized in a dashboard. The water sensors' position relative to the onshore data receiving equipment will be changed, and the availability to transfer the data from multiple sites in an oyster farm will be validated.

The end user can view the data in the dashboard at any time and can do that using different devices. The water quality monitoring system allows the end user to check the status of the environment without the need to be on-site in an oyster farm.

The main objective of the test scenario is the successful transfer of the data from the water sensor to the database using LoRaWAN and satellite networks and the visualization of the data in the dashboard. The goals of the test are to estimate the system's main network, service and resource usage parameters.

Testing will not require the use of any additional hardware. Only the hardware which is already used for the implementation of the system will be used. The raft and solar panels from the oyster farm will be used to deploy the water sensors. The built-in software for estimating network, service and resource usage characteristics will be used. Testing will be carried out by the personnel of the UC solution provider and the farmer or his staff. The test scenario is described in Table 18.

Table 18: UC5 Test Scenarios for Technology Mixtures

Scenario 1	Testing data transfer capabilities and efficiency of the remote water monitoring system.		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
The remote and autonomous water quality monitoring system is deployed on-site – at the oyster farm. Water quality parameters are estimated, and collected data is transferred to the dedicated database where the data is picked up and visualised for the end user. A combination of LoRaWAN and satellite networks is used for data transfer.	The data is successfully transferred via LoRaWAN and satellite networks from the deployed water sensors to the database. The data is successfully taken from the database and visualised on Grafana dashboard.	TBC	Testing will be carried out within a few days' time to ensure the stability and reliability of data collection and transfer.

10.3.1 UC5 Data Definition

The data collected within the UC is information on the water quality parameters. The specific parameters of water quality whose data is gathered depends on the design of the systems, which in turn depends on the requirements of the end user. In the specific case of the UC5, multiple water quality parameters are to be measured: dissolved oxygen, pH, chlorophyll level, salinity, temperature, and turbidity. Depending on the specific parameter, the data of the change of conductivity, optical transparency, and pressure is measured. The correlation between the registered change and the specific parameter value is an intrinsic property of the water sensors.

The data collected by all sensors is in numerical format and stored in a PostgreSQL library. Using an API, the data is taken from the database and is visualized in a Grafana-based dashboard.

The data is not sensitive since the body of water is natural. Therefore, specific restrictions or security measures need to be implemented.

10.4 UC5 Challenges, Risks and Assumptions

Challenges:

- Ensuring the proper device placement for satellite connectivity can be challenging. The satellite connectivity enabler has to be placed in an open space for a reliable communication.

Risks:

- Power outages can hinder data transfer which in turn can lead to a missed window for satellite data transfer.

10.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Overview of XGain UC5

10.5.1 Technology mixture testing KPIs

The technology mixture will be tested on several technical KPIs. The KPIs, their envisioned values and the means of their estimation are presented in Table 19. This is a tentative selection and will be better defined after the initiation of the testing period.

Table 19: UC5 Technology Mixture Testing KPIs

KPI	Target value	Calculation method	Validation Method
Resource use	CPU usage: 10 % RAM usage: 1.5 GB Power consumption: ~50 W	Resource utilisation will be measured using built-in commands, such as "top command" and estimation of edge device load.	Multiple tests performed spanning a few days.
E2E Response Time	Average 5 h	The time between the data package sending and the time when it was shown to the end-user will be calculated.	Multiple tests performed spanning a few days.
Service Availability	On average, above 95 %	Availability will be calculated by estimating the period of time the connection and data transfer were available considering the revisiting time of the satellite.	Multiple tests performed spanning a few days.
Service Reliability	On average, above 95 %	When transmitting data, we include the timestamp indicating the moment the data packet was created. Upon receiving the data packet, we can calculate the processing time, enabling us to determine the count of requests that were successfully processed within the expected time frame.	Multiple tests performed spanning a few days.

10.5.2 Impact assessment KPIs

A tentative selection of KPIs to evaluate impact assessment in UC5 has been made, shown in Table 20. The final KPIs to measure will be better defined after the start of UC execution.

Table 20: UC5 impact assessment KPIs

Impact	KPI	Calculation method	Validation method
Economic	Increase in aquaculture production or profitability	Estimate the production yield increase or production saved by implementing the technology solution.	Estimate the change in production and profitability within the same duration of not-using and using the solution.
Economic	Cost reduction in operations	Evaluate the reduction of operational costs due to automation.	Estimate the change in costs of operations within the same duration of not-using and using the solution.
Environmental	Reduction in production of CO ₂	Evaluate the reduction of CO ₂ coming from the reduced resource consumption.	Calculate the change in CO ₂ emissions within the same duration of not-using and using the solution.
Environmental	Increase in resource efficiency	Measure resource efficiency in aquaculture operations.	Calculate the change in resource efficiency within the same duration of not-using and using the solution.
Technological	Network expansion	Measure the availability of LoRaWAN network in the aquaculture area.	Estimate the expansion of the connectivity options before and after solution implementation.
Technological	Increased volume of data and number of measurements	Measure the ratio of pre- and post-innovation amount of relative data.	Estimate the increase in the water quality data within the same period before and after solution implementation.
Social	Increased information and data sharing (Access to immaterial resources)	Estimate the number of visits to the dashboard.	Calculate visits to the dashboard through a defined period of time.

11 XGain UC 6: Livestock and Farming (Belgium)

11.1 Use Case 6 Overview, Objectives and Expected Outcome

11.1.1 UC6 overview and set-up

Flanders has a high population density (492 /km²), however pastures are mostly situated in less populated areas, but frequently there are some houses, roads or walking areas next to the pastures. Therefore, the fields of a farmers are mostly a network of small patches distributed in the region and not necessarily connected to each other. The private 4G network covers Flanders completely, however locally network connectivity and reliability might not meet the expectations. Private 5G is being rolled out but at very slow pace and is only accessible in some cities and next to important highways. A recent survey showed that a large part (>75%) of Flemish farmers recognize that grazing is beneficial for the welfare of their cows, however the number of farms with grazing cattle is decreasing. The uncertainty of feedstock (quantity and quality) is one of the main restrictions for farmers to incorporate grazing into their management.

11.1.2 UC6 services.

By developing digital tools that allow farmers to better monitor welfare and behaviour of their herd this UC aims to contribute improved farm management for farmers with grazing cattle.

11.1.3 Key Roles and Interactions within UC6

EVILVO is the only contributor to this UC and is responsible for the development and deployment of the setup at the pasture as well as setting up the database server (Postgres) and the connection over mobile network. EVILO is also responsible for the planning of the UC, the technical evaluation of the technology mixture as well as the impact assessment.

11.1.4 Implementation Plan

Figure 13 provides an overview of the general implantation and test plan for the Belgian UC. It comprises the development of the animal detection and localisation algorithm, connecting to the database server with an API and mobile network as well as the reliability testing and measuring the system data throughput and energy consumption.

Figure 13: UC6 Implementation Plan

11.2 Mapping of UC6 with KFT functionalities

The Belgian UC assesses the impact on farm and community level of digital connectivity solutions and edge processing devices with respect to livestock health and farm management. Farmers or companies developing a digital shepherd to monitor grazing cattle could benefit from the KFT in multiple ways. Grazing is farm management decision and could be implanted in many different ways, e.g. cows can be placed on in a specific zone of a pasture during daytime or farmers could choose allow free access to a pasture next to the barn all day long. Also, the period in which cows are placed on a pasture could alter from farm to farm. The KFT should thus allow end-users to provide this information as it influences the conditions in which the technology mixture is deployed. There is also a great difference between farmers’ preferences towards innovative solutions, economic return and environmental impact. The KFT should adjust its proposed technology based on their preferences. Finally, some farmers might already have subscriptions to a mobile network which determines its capacity. Additionally, public 5G networks are being rolled-out but the coverage and performance can vary greatly depending on the location. So, the KFT should be regularly updated with the latest information about this as well as providing the opportunity to the end-users to define maximum consumption of the proposed solutions.

11.3 UC6 Test Scenarios

A test scenario could be to deploy a camera setup with an edge processing device in a pasture. The visual information is processed locally using AI detection models to identify the behavior (grazing, lying, standing) and the location of individual cows. Based on the potential update frequency and data throughput the data will first be aggregated and then send to the Postgis database which is accessed through an API. The stored data will be made available in an online dashboard (e.g. Grafana), it will visualize over a user-defined period the grazing intensity across the pasture.

Information about the grazing intensity and location will be coupled with local weather information from a private owned weather station at EVILVO or from an online database if the pasture is far from the institute. Additionally, using a UAV equipped with a multi spectral camera or satellite data the biomass will be assessed at regular time intervals to link with the grazing maps. This test scenario is summarized in Table 21 below.

Table 21: UC5 Test Scenarios for Technology Mixtures

Scenario 1	Deploy a camera setup with an edge processing device in a pasture		
Scenario Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Additional Notes
A camera setup is installed at a pasture to monitor the grazing cattle continuously. The images are processed locally on an edge device and the results are sent to a database that can also be accessed through a dashboard for data visualisation	The end-user can get regular updates about the grazing location and intensity through a visual dashboard.	TBC	

11.3.1 UC6 Data Definition

During the project mainly images and will be collected with a camera system. The acquired images and videos will be stored on the local file server of EVILVO. Part of the images will be labelled to train custom detection models on. In the database setup which will run on the Postgres server of EVILVO we will keep track of the data used to train the model as well as some meta data about the training process (epochs, batch size, model architecture, duration, time started) and model performance (MAP50, precision & recall). These models will run on edge computing device to which a camera is connected. To monitor the cattle (location & behaviour) the industrial camera with a specific lens will be placed in a field with a certain orientation. Camera and lens parameters (intrinsic) as the camera position and orientation (extrinsic) will be stored on the local file server. Information about the cows' position and behaviour will be saved in a postgres database. All data sources will be linked with a unique identifier and a pre-defined cardinality. This database should ensure reusability of the data with limited access credentials.

11.4 UC6 Challenges, Risks and Assumptions

Challenges:

- Because the grazing areas in Flanders are mostly small patches setup of the camera setup might be difficult
- Most of the UC is based on many in-house development as no commercial solutions exist for software and hardware.
- Weather conditions influence the preference of farmers for putting their cattle outside.

Risks:

- A recent study showed that grazing is declining in Flanders due to economic and farm management decisions.
- Grazing is seasonally bound so technology testing is also bound to the period which might cause difficulties to conduct the full range of tests.
- There is strong political debate ongoing in Flanders on the nitrogen pollution of livestock which can cause farmers to be reluctant to cooperate researchers as well as alter their expectations for technological innovations.

Assumptions:

- We make the assumption that the test surrounding provides us a good image for effectiveness and impact of the technology.
- For the deployment of the use, we rely on a public network and assume the network performance is reliable at the test location.

11.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Overview of XGain UC6

11.5.1 Technology mixture testing KPIs

The technological KPIs defined in the planning stage for the testing of technology mixtures in the field for UC6 are shown below in Table 22. This is a tentative selection and will be better defined after the initiation of the testing period.

Table 22: UC6 Technology Mixture Testing KPIs

KPI	Target Value	Calculation method	Validation method
Data throughput	< 50GB/month	Measure increase in the database size during deployment.	Deploy the setup at a pasture and continuously send data to the database.
Peak upload	< 50 Mbps	Determine bit size of largest data package and multiply with sensor frequency.	Deploy setup and log the size of each data package to determine the maximal size.
Update frequency	< 1h (key indicators) < 200 ms (video streaming)	Check largest time interval in the database. Key indicators should be updated at least every hour. Video streaming should be available on-demand with a latency below the defined KPI target value.	Every data package (key indicators or image) will be timestamped when captured by measuring the time difference with the time when received allows to determine the update frequency.
Reliability	>95%	Log network availability during test period and keep track of manual maintenance requirements. This target value should be met during grazing season (April – September).	Check in the database when there was an outage or no data was transferred.

11.5.2 Impact assessment KPIs

A tentative selection of KPIs to evaluate impact assessment in UC6 has been made, shown in Table 23. The final KPIs to measure will be better defined after the start of UC execution.

Table 23: UC6 impact assessment KPIs

Impact	KPI	Calculation method	Validation method
Technological	Detection Accuracy	Ratio of the true positive predictions and the actual cows	Acquire images over a certain period use the model to detect cows and compare with manually labelled data
Technological	Localisation accuracy	Calculate difference between estimated position with RTK-GPS determined positions	The estimated position should be on average not more than 1m away from the true position
Technological	Behaviour identification	Compare predictions with ground truth labels	Accuracy should be greater than 85% to be acceptable
Social	Skill development	Count number of farmers	At least 30 farmers should be informed

		present at workshops/events	about the potential of AI for farm management and livestock welfare
Social	Community support	Count number of other people directly reached during workshops/events	At least 300 people should be informed about the potential of AI for farm management and livestock welfare
Economic	System cost	Determine hardware cost	Total cost of single setup could not exceed €1000
Environmental	CO ₂ sequestration	Estimate pasture CO ₂ sequestration based on biomass development	TBD
Environmental	Power consumption	Measure the systems power consumption over week and extrapolate to the grazing season	Use smart plug to measure power consumption

12 Conclusions

The completion of Deliverable D5.1 marks a significant step in the XGain testing and validation work, providing a detailed and comprehensive insight into the planning, setup, and operational management strategies for the upcoming field trials. The deliverable underscores the project's commitment to achieving its objectives, with a particular focus on the validation of the XGain ecosystem of technologies in diverse real-world scenarios, represented by 6 unique and diverse UCs. The planning and setup handbook serves as a guiding document for the field trials, ensuring that each UC is well-aligned with the overarching project goals. The emphasis on social acceptance, technological validation, and business model analysis reflects the holistic approach of the XGain project, acknowledging the diverse stakeholders involved.

The testing and validation plan outlines the different validation “layers” that need to be addressed, including the testing and validation of technology mixtures, the KFT and its outputs, and the social acceptance and impact assessment. In parallel, it provides tools, procedures and a time plan of activities with which the UCs need to be aligned. Based on this strategy, during this preparatory phase, UCs have identified several KPIs and test scenarios related to the technologies, KFT output, and impact assessment validation, along with specific implementation plans, challenges, risks, assumptions, and key roles and interactions within each UC. Furthermore, an overview of each UC has been provided, in terms of topology, socio-demographic profile, and service requirements, which will help in mapping of UC needs to KFT functionalities and in impact assessment analysis. Lastly, the managing and monitoring procedures of WP5 activities has been discussed, with particular emphasis on the PDCA cycle and the agile methodology used in the validation work.

In conclusion, the completion of this deliverable and the planning and preparatory phase signifies the initiation of Phase 1 of testing and validation. Feedback from this phase will be used to make any necessary refinements to the testing plan, and better define testing procedures and KPIs, to ensure that the activities always align to the expected outcomes. These updates of the plan, as well as the initial results from the testing activities will be reported in the update version of this deliverable, D5.2, in month 26.